

INNOVATIVE LARGE-SCALE PRODUCTION OF AFFORDABLE CLEAN BURNING SOLID BIOFUEL AND WATER IN SOUTHERN AFRICA

Transforming bush encroachment from a problem into a secure and sustainable energy source

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ABSTRACT

Countries across Southern Africa are increasingly suffering from encroachment of native bush overgrowth and of invasive species. This unwanted woody biomass competes with livestock and wildlife for water, contributes to soil erosion, and threatens natural habitats and local savannah ecosystems. However, the cost to clear bush exceeds the immediate benefits of increased agricultural productivity. The SteamBioAfrica project seeks to tackle bush encroachment by transforming the bush and invasive biomass into solid a clean burning biofuel and water.

This report composes deliverable D10.1 of WP10. The objective of WP10 is to identify existing value chains to enable large scale commercialisation of the proposed solid biofuel. Deliverable 10.1 analyses existing value chains of solid cooking and heating energy sources (particularly of charcoal and firewood) in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa, with particular focus on the downstream value chain (retail and distribution sector). The main source of data collection for this report is a baseline survey on the commercialisation of cooking and heating energy sources carried out in selected rural, peri-urban and urban areas in the three countries. Target groups included the retail sector: wholesalers, small-scale retailers, kiosks and open-air stalls, as well as household consumers. Other sources of data collection include expert interviews and grey literature.

Findings of the analysis indicate that rural households commonly use firewood as one of the main sources of energy for heating and cooking. However, this finding does not necessarily reflect the real usage of firewood in rural areas, which can be higher than the baseline survey result, because many rural consumers often collect firewood themselves. Urban and peri-urban households use electricity and/or LPG as their main source of energy for heating and cooking. Compared to firewood, charcoal is a costly cooking and heating energy source. Urban and peri-urban households commonly use charcoal only for leisure activities (barbecue, parties).

To facilitate the long-term commercialisation of the proposed solid biofuel it is important to increase the attractiveness of the product by, for example, offering free delivery services, online selling systems, diverse payment options (cash, 'pay later' options, phone payments) and offer a reliable supply of the product, particularly in rural areas. Moreover, it is key to offer fair and competitive prices, especially in rural areas, where potential customers generally still use firewood, which they can collect themselves for free. Any positive health aspect of the solid biofuel (e.g., generating less smoke or having higher calorific value) might be useful in the biofuel marketing.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Countries across Southern Africa are increasingly suffering from encroachment of native bush overgrowth and of invasive species. This unwanted woody biomass competes with livestock and wildlife for water, contributes to soil erosion, and threatens natural habitats and local savannah ecosystems. However, the cost to clear bush exceeds the immediate benefits of increased agricultural productivity. Hence, there is a pressing need to create increased value from harvested bush. The EU Horizon SteamBioAfrica project seeks to tackle the crisis caused by unwanted woody biomass overgrowth by creating more value from the biomass than it costs to harvest. This will be achieved by transforming the bush and invasive biomass into solid a clean burning biofuel and water. Thereby, the project will create improved access to high value, clean, secure, and affordable renewable energy sources in Namibia, Botswana, and South Africa. The transformation of woody bush into a sustainable and secure clean bioenergy supply, will not only increase the value of the harvested bush through the production of biofuel, but also through land restoration. In doing so, the project will help address other environmental and societal challenges in the region such as impacts of climate change, energy insecurity, water shortages, social exclusion and unemployment.

This report composes Deliverable 10.1 of Work Package 10 (WP10) of SteamBioAfrica project. The main objective of **WP10** is to identify existing value chains and gaps that need to be filled, to enable large scale commercialisation of the proposed solid biofuel. **Deliverable 10.1** focuses on the downstream value chain of cooking and heating energy sources (charcoal and firewood). It analyses **existing value chains of solid cooking and heating energy sources** in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa, with particular focus on the **retail and distribution sector**. The analysis sheds light on fuel commercialisation and consumption trends, and offers insights into potential marketing strategies, distribution channels and methods, product pricing and supply chains to facilitate the commercialisation of the proposed solid biofuel in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa.

Results of the value chain mapping and analysis indicate that in **Botswana**, particularly rural household consumers use **firewood** as one of the main energy sources of cooking and heating. Especially in areas where the access to other types of energy sources tends to be limited, firewood is commonly used as energy source for cooking. It is estimated that 46% households in Botswana use firewood. In rural areas, the use of firewood reaches up to 77% of the households (Mphinyane et al., 2018).

Households in urban and peri-urban areas of Botswana rely mostly on electricity and LPG for cooking and heating, and tend to only use **charcoal** for barbecuing. In rural areas, however, charcoal is rarely used since it is comparatively more expensive than firewood, which in many cases is collected by households themselves. Occasionally urban and peri-urban households use firewood to cook traditional food. These consumers buy firewood from small retail shops, online shops and occasionally from gas stations where price tends to be slightly higher compared to small retail shops or online sellers.

Initial strategies for the commercialisation of the new solid biofuel in Botswana should not target households as main consumers. To build the value chains for long-term commercialisation of the new solid biofuel, clear **incentives for household consumers** in urban, peri-urban and especially rural areas are essential. Hence, while the SHS technology is still in its initial phase, this report proposes **industrial consumers** as initial key consumer group to drive a demand for the solid biofuel.

Regarding **Namibia**, the value chain mapping and analysis shows that the country is an important producer and exporter of **charcoal** to Botswana and South Africa. Charcoal is widely used by household consumers living in urban and peri-urban areas for leisure activities such as barbecues (braai'ing). Charcoal is also used by some low-income households for cooking in pots. However, in rural areas, households mainly use firewood for cooking and heating. The majority of Namibia's charcoal is destined for export due to high international demand. Compared to charcoal, **firewood** is a more affordable energy source. Despite it being highly popular in rural areas, the commercial demand for firewood is low because most households tend to collect firewood instead of buying it. Thus, the commercialisation of the new solid biofuel in Namibia will have to compete with the well-established charcoal industry and offer comparatively fairer prices than those of firewood. Similar strategy as in Botswana can be employed, where industrial consumers (e.g., dairy and brewery companies) can be targeted as to create demand for the solid biofuel.

In **South Africa**, households in urban and rural areas generally use electricity and LPG as their main sources of energy for cooking and heating. Similar to Botswana and Namibia, charcoal is mainly used by consumers in urban (and to a lesser degree in peri-urban areas) for leisure activities such as barbecues (braai'ing). In addition, South Africa is a charcoal producer, importer and exporter country. Charcoal in South Africa is produced by community-based enterprises, which offer their product to wholesalers and distribution centres. The imported charcoal

comes mainly from Namibia. For a long-term commercialisation of the new solid biofuel, it is important to consider that households rely heavily on electricity and gas for cooking and heating. Hence, shifting to a different energy source will require clear incentives. **These incentives can be integrated in the retail and distribution sector**, for example by offering delivery services or alternative and easy payment methods, besides an affordable price.

Existing value chains in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa offer different opportunities for the commercialisation of the new solid biofuel. The analysis indicates that building on the existing value chains of charcoal (and, to some extent, of firewood) and improving the 'hot spots' observed in the chains (by offering an efficient, clean and affordable energy source alternative) can facilitate a wide-scale commercialisation of the solid biofuel. For this, it is important to increase the attractiveness of the product. For example, by offering free delivery services, online selling systems, diverse payment options (cash, 'pay later' options, phone payments) and offer a reliable supply of the product, particularly in rural areas. Moreover, it is key to offer fair and competitive prices, especially in rural areas, where potential customers have another alternative, i.e., firewood.

PROJECT BACKGROUND

1

Countries in Southern Africa are increasingly suffering from the encroachment of native bush overgrowth and of invasive species. The SteamBioAfrica seeks to tackle the challenge by creating more value out of the biomass than the costs of harvesting it. Through the superheated steam technology, the project will transform the biomass into clean burning solid biofuel and water.

Countries across Southern Africa are increasingly suffering from encroachment of native bush overgrowth and of invasive species. This unwanted woody biomass competes with livestock and wildlife for water, contributes to soil erosion, and threatens natural habitats and local savannah ecosystems. However, combating and controlling unwanted woody biomass overgrowth is costly, it involves intensive manual labour. Hence, there is a pressing need to create increased value from harvested woody biomass.

With the support of the European Union's Horizon 2020 Program the SteamBioAfrica project was launched in September 2021. It involves an EU-Africa industry research collaboration of fifteen partners working together. SteamBioAfrica seeks to tackle this crisis caused by unwanted overgrowth by creating more value from the biomass than it costs to harvest. These ambitions will also help to address other environmental and societal challenges in the region such as impact of climate change, energy insecurity, water shortages, social inclusion and unemployment. This will be achieved by transforming the bush and invasive biomass into clean burning solid biofuel and water.

The SteamBioAfrica project involves an innovative application of Superheated Steam (SHS) processing technology at mild pyrolytic conditions (torrefaction) to transform this woody biomass into a fuel with higher calorific value and that burns with few harmful emissions. The process also produces a condensate rich in chemicals and water. It is projected that post project commercial scale replication will eventually result. This will lead to improved access to high value, clean, secure, and affordable renewable energy sources in Namibia, Botswana, and South Africa. Achieving these ambitions will promote sustainable harvesting and land management practices and stimulate effective land restoration.

The project's business plan is included within the initial Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDER). It projects that within ten years after the end of the project, Southern Africa will have a Superheated Steam processing and operating capacity of 350 tonnes/hour. This would result in over 6,300 km² of restored land (7.6 million tonnes CO₂eq saving), over 40 million tonnes of clean burning solid biofuel (9.2 million tonnes CO₂eq saving), 1,900 m³ of recovered water and 6,800 new jobs.

1.1 OBJECTIVES OF WORK PACKAGE 10

The main objective of WP10 is to identify existing value chains and gaps that need to be filled, to enable large scale commercial implementation of SHS processing of bush and other woody biomass into sustainable clean burning solid biofuel. This will involve:

- Mapping the downstream value chain and identify impact groups and areas for the biofuel commercialisation.
- Creating a pool of local workforce with the skills required to support the long-term commercial deployment and feedstock supply of the SHS technology in Southern Africa.
- Identifying and developing viable localised business models to commercialise the solid biofuel into the domestic household market. This will focus on micro-enterprises (MSMEs) and job creation.
- Engaging locally with government and policy makers to identify policies that will support the project implementation and impact.
- Identifying financial instruments that can support local implementation of the project results, including long-term post-project perspectives.

To ensure a long-term viability of the biofuel that will be demonstrated in this project (WP5), WP 10 partners seek to identify technical and business-related gaps and needs in local skills and workforce. This will facilitate them to then enable the design and delivery of training and capacity building programs. Technical training will include woody biomass harvesting and land management modules for farmers, as well as modules on core basic scientific technical and engineering skills. This will provide basic competences that further on-site specific training to support the operation and maintenance of the SHS based Biomass Processing plant. The business facing training programmes will focus on micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs). These will include youth and women-led enterprises. They will offer capacity building modules that will support a wide-scale commercialisation of the new solid biofuel within the domestic retail sectors and the development of sustainable and inclusive business models.

This report composes deliverable D10.1 of WP10. Deliverable 10.1 focuses on the downstream commercialisation of cooking and heating energy sources (charcoal and firewood) to identify and map existing value chains in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa. This mapping will facilitate the identification of impact groups that can support a wide-scale commercialisation of the novel solid biofuel that will be demonstrated in this project. In other words, the report will analyse **existing value**

chains of solid cooking and heating energy sources in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa, with particular focus on the **retail and distribution sector**. The focus of deliverable 10.1 on charcoal and/or firewood for the analysis of existing value chains is due to the fact that the use of these energy sources is relatively similar to the use of the proposed solid biofuel. Hence, commercialisation target groups might be similar (wholesaler, retailers, consumers) and the commercialisation of the proposed solid biofuel might be able to build upon existing value chain structures of charcoal and firewood.

The value chain analysis can:

- Reveal any underlying causes of challenges and bottlenecks,
- Allow understanding incentives of market actors to develop alternative strategies and,
- Help create improved processes, highlight risks and opportunities and identify leverage points for interventions (ILO, 2015:10).

The purpose behind analysing existing value chains is to:

- Identify relevant market actors (retail and distribution) along the value chains of similar (competing) products
- Explore actors' incentives and motivations,
- Understand underlying dynamics and relationships among actors, and
- Explore challenges and opportunities for innovation to develop sustainable and inclusive value chains for future wide-scale commercialization of the proposed solid biofuel.

This analysis places emphasis on **the end market and commercialisation** of cooking and heating energy sources. Through the analysis, we can identify any fuel commercialisation and consumption trends and gain insights into potential marketing strategies, distribution channels and methods, product pricing and supply chains.

Work Package 10 is linked to Work Package 9. Work Package 9 aims to assess the potential market for solid biofuel produced by the SHS process from bush and other woody biomass in the **domestic household sector**. WP 9 focuses on identifying factors influencing consumer behaviour and market acceptance of this fuel. In addition, it identifies and engages strategically with key value chain actors in the three participating African countries. It does this across rural, urban, and peri-urban areas to create local demand and markets for the solid biofuel produced by SHS processed biomass.

1.2 ACTIVITIES AND METHODOLOGY

This report is based on mixed methods of qualitative and quantitative data analysis. The main sources of data collection are a baseline survey, interviews with key informants and reviews of documents and grey literature. The collected qualitative data went through a process of triangulation to gain different insights about the same phenomenon and complement as well as validate the gathered information. The collected quantitative raw data went through frequency analysis using SAS (Statistical Analysis System) version 9.4 (2020) for the categorical variables for each country. Once processed, all of the data was compiled and contrasted. The data was then analysed using abductive reasoning. Conclusions were then reached through logical inference based on a set of observations and seeking the most likely and simplest inference from the observations. Results of the data analysis provide insights into the mapping of existing and relevant value chains. This enabled profiling of impact groups, and identification of hotspots and sweet spots in the value chains. This led to the development of new, sustainable and inclusive value chains for future wide-scale commercialisation of the novel solid biofuel in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa.

1.2.1 DATA COLLECTION

The overall data collection was coordinated by BITRI (Botswana Institute for Technology Research and Innovation). Ekasi was responsible for on the ground data collection in South Africa. NUST (Namibia University of Science and Technology) and N-BiG (Namibia Biomass Industry Group) were responsible for this work in Namibia. The survey consisted of a cross-sectional household survey carried out within two weeks in the three countries.

The baseline statistical surveys were conducted in Botswana, South Africa and Namibia from 7th to 26th February 2022. in urban, sub-urban and rural localities. The surveys covered (1) households, (2) wholesalers and (3) small-scale businesses comprising retailers, kiosks, and open-air stall sellers in urban, peri-urban and rural areas. The WP9 surveys mainly targeted household consumers, WP10 targeted mainly the retail and distribution sector (wholesalers and small-scale retailers, kiosks and open-air stalls)

A simple random sampling method was used in the random selection of the respondents. Pilot studies were undertaken before the main survey. The results from these pilot studies were then used to modify and improve on the final questionnaires.

Criteria for selection of household respondent:

1. Household member above 18 years old,
2. Typically lived in the household.
3. Available and willing to be interviewed

Criteria for selection of retail respondent:

1. Representative of the business that sells cooking and heating energy sources
2. Managerial knowledge (knowledge about prices, suppliers, brands, etc)
3. Available and willing to be interviewed

The surveys were face-to-face interviews with respondents. These were undertaken by trained project field officers who explained to respondents the background of the survey. Respondents were requested to read and sign a consent form for the interview to proceed i.e., informed consent.

The questionnaires included questions about existing consumption patterns and commercialisation of cooking and heating energy sources. Questions were focused on widely used (“popular”) energy sources, supply chains, pricing, packaging, labels and branding, consumer preferences, vendor characteristics, among others (for more information see Appendix 1).

Target Group	Botswana	Namibia	South Africa	Total
Households	N=99	N=60	N=39	N=198
Wholesaler	N=13	N=5	N=10	N=28
Small scale retailers	N=48	N=15	N=10	N=73
Total	N=160	N=80	N=59	N=299

Table 1 Sample size per country per target group (Source: BITRI)

The survey sample size was 299 (see Table 1) with respondents from households, wholesalers and retailers. Botswana provided the largest population sample size with 161 respondents. Namibia and South Africa both provided sample sizes of 80 respondents. The sample size was defined based on the project’s timeframe and availability of (human and economic) resources.

In Botswana, the project field officers held a mini workshop with the assigned statistician on how to capture data on the questionnaires into an MS Excel spreadsheet template. Each data column (the variables for analysis) in the

worksheet were mapped to the corresponding question of the questionnaire. In the case of questions with multiple options, each option had a separate data column to enable all data to be captured. The standardized data entry systems and database structures were shared with partners in South Africa and Namibia for data entry.

The raw data from closed-ended questions of the questionnaire were subjected to frequency analysis (descriptive statistics) and the chi-square test of goodness of fit and of independence using SAS (Statistical Analysis System) version 9.4 (2020) for the categorical variables for each country. The results of the analysis were populated into standardized tables created based on the questionnaire. For age, the ages of respondents were first grouped accordingly e.g., into Youth and Adult categories, and frequency analysis and chi-square tests done them. The chi-square test excluded all counts shown under Not stated in the tables as these were treated as missing values or non-replies.

The quantitative data analyses were conducted on data combined for the three countries and desegregated by **age** (i.e., Youth or Adult with 35 years as the cut of age between Youth and Adult), and by **location** (i.e., Urban, Sub-Urban and Rural). The open-ended questions were analysed manually (qualitative data analysis) by reading through each questionnaire and compiling the frequencies. The level of significance for all inferences of the statistical tests was $\alpha = 0.05$. The p-value and degrees of freedom (df) for each test (if valid) is shown at the bottom of each table. If p-value is less than 0.05 then the classes/categories are significant.

Response Rate

Country	Target Sample Size	No. of household interviews completed	Household response rate %
Botswana	60	99	165.0
Namibia	60	60	100.0
South Africa	60	39	65.0
Total	180	198	110.0

**Response rates above 100% are indicative of the extra interviews conducted in Botswana.*

Table 2 Target and actual sample size, and response rate for the household survey (Source: BITRI)

Country	Target Sample Size	No. of retail interviews completed	Retail response rate %
Botswana	15-25	48	320 - 192
Namibia	15-25	15	100 - 60
South Africa	15-25	10	67 - 40
Total	45-75	73	162 - 97

**Response rates above 100% are indicative of the extra interviews conducted in Botswana.*

Table 3 Target and actual sample size and response rate for the retail survey (Source: BITRI)

Country	Target Sample Size	No. of wholesalers' interviews completed	Wholesalers' response rate %
Botswana	15-25	13	87-52
Namibia	15-25	5	33-20
South Africa	15-25	10	67-40
Total	45-75	28	62-37

**Response rates above 100% are indicative of the extra interviews conducted in Botswana.*

Table 4 Target and actual sample size, and response rate for the wholesalers' survey (Source: BITRI)

The above presented tables and information about data collection were facilitated by BITRI.

Interviews with key informants

Key informant interviews were conducted online by CSCP using informal and semi-structured formats. The interviews took place in March and April 2022. In total five interviews took place with expert informants with knowledge on firewood and charcoal value chains in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa. All interviews took between 30-60 minutes, they provided insights which were gathered on the on the dynamics of actors involved with firewood and charcoal, and with downstream commercialisation. Based on the interviews the downstream commercialisation of value chain maps for firewood and charcoal were prepared.

Review of documents and grey literature

By reviewing a variety of published literature additional data was collated. Sources included reports and newspaper articles as well as grey literature. This covered country and region-specific trends relating to

- the use of renewable energy sources,
- green transition
- access to clean and affordable energy sources
- energy poverty,
- causes and impact of unwanted woody biomass overgrowth,
- unwanted woody biomass overgrowth related land use practices and management,
- woody biomass harvesting methods,
- use of biomass for renewable energy,
- socio-economic and other relevant topics.

1.2.2 HOTSPOT ANALYSIS FOR VALUE CHAIN DEVELOPMENT OF SOLID BIOFUEL

This study used hotspot analysis to identify risks, gaps, challenges, and opportunities along existing value chains related to cooking and heating energy sources. This enabled the development of the downstream section of the biomass-based value chain. Hotspots analysis is a helpful and effective tool. It enables the identification of areas to be prioritised for action. Literature does not offer a common approach to hotspots analysis. However, the hotspot analysis in this study covered:

- mapping and in-depth analysis of existing value chains of cooking and heating energy sources in Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa
- the identification of main impact (customer preferences, existing structures and dynamics) within the value chains, similarities, and differences among the different value chains,
- opportunities for improvement and references for benchmarking, particularly in relation to the promotion of social inclusion and gender balance, as the reduction of energy poverty.

The hotspots refer to gaps and challenges that can negatively impact the development of the downstream of the solid biofuel value chain and commercial success of the novel biofuel post project three countries covered. The downstream of the biomass-based value chain includes the wholesaling, the retailing and, the consumption (household consumers). By understanding “what and where”, the hotspots can be found in this downstream. This will help the project to address

challenges with potential to negatively impact on the project's commercial potential. By focussing on these hotspots (challenges), the project will be able to facilitate market pull and demand. This demand will then in turn support the project commercial ambitions. A consumer market demand for the novel solid biofuel will stimulate the long-term deployment of SHS processing capacity across wider Southern African region.

1.3 ETHICS

All activities of data collection (questionnaires, survey, key informant interviews) for this report were carried out in compliance with ethics requirements established in Work Package 13 of the SteamBioAfrica project.

Activities to gain further insights and understand buying and consumption patterns of communities from different socio-economic sectors across Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa involved the participation of determined target groups. These included household consumers (communities in rural, urban, and peri-urban areas) and company consumers (retailers, distributors, wholesalers).

Using an information and consent form (Appendix 1), participants were informed of the study purpose and how their data will be used. The information and consent form indicated that the participation in the activities was completely voluntary (free informed consent) and that participants had the option to opt out of the research at any time. They were provided with contact details in case they have any concerns after the activities have taken place. Participants were informed that they had the option to have their data withdrawn from the study if they wanted in the future. Participants were also advised that all data from surveys will be anonymised and stored securely, and will be excluded from the open data pilot. No primary data will be used in any publication.

PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND STUDY AREAS

2

Unwanted woody biomass overgrowth has been widely reported across Southern Africa including in Namibia, South Africa and Botswana. This overgrowth significantly alters the landscapes, biodiversity, and ability of grassland and savanna ecosystems to deliver ecosystem goods and services including nutrient cycling, grazing, hydrological services and carbon storage.

2.1 UNWANTED WOODY BIOMASS OVERGROWTH IN NAMIBIA, BOTSWANA AND SOUTH AFRICA

The overgrowth of unwanted woody biomass (which includes bush encroachment and the expansion of invasive woody species) significantly alters the landscapes, the biodiversity, and the ability of grassland and savanna ecosystems to deliver ecosystem goods and services including nutrient cycling, grazing, hydrological services and carbon storage (DEA, 2019, p. 38) causing serious environmental and economic problems. Thus, it is commonly related to loss in soil fertility and it used as an indicator of land degradation (MEA, 2005; Dube, 2007; ZEF, 2016).

**Encroached areas
can lose 44 million
litres/year/ha of
groundwater**

Concerns regarding the increasing woody biomass overgrowth especially in Southern Africa emerged in the 1980s (Welz, 2013; ZEF, 2016). Unwanted woody biomass overgrowth degrades over 120 million ha across Southern Africa: It stifles herbaceous plants, reduces biodiversity, depletes groundwater reserves, and degrades the soil (The Southern Times, 2020). Its negative ecosystem impact undermines surrounding communities' food and water security (Sebitloane et al., 2020). Encroachment diminishes and weakens productive farmland and rangelands, reducing livestock productivity (Mugasi et al., 2000). At its extreme it leads to the displacement of smallholder farmers to live in poverty on the edge of townships. Encroached areas can lose over 44 million litres/year/ha of groundwater through evapotranspiration (Honsbein & Lindeque, 2017). This threatens the already fragile water balance in these semi-arid regions. The regions vulnerability was clearly demonstrated when drought induced crop failures led to nearly 45 million people across Southern Africa receiving food aid in December 2019 (Reuters, 2019). A South African government report recommended it being classified as a form of land degradation under the UN commitments (DEA, 2019)¹.

Unwanted woody biomass overgrowth has been widely reported across Southern Africa (Wigley et al., 2009) including in Namibia, South Africa and also Botswana (Shikangalah & Mapani, 2020, p. 2). **Namibia**, has lost over 45 million ha of land due to unwanted woody biomass overgrowth (increasing 1.5 million ha per year) (Beltran, 2015; N-BIG, 2020). All of Namibia's territory is affected by woody biomass overgrowth, but central parts of Namibia are especially affected (Welz, 2013; N-BIG, 2020). It is one of the country's most critical problems (Uchezuba et al., 2019, Huang et al., 2018) since it has led to massive land deterioration and to the threat of massive ecological and economical damage (De Wet, 2015, Mendelsohn

¹ For more information refer to Grant Agreement (Nr. 101036401 — SteamBioAfrica — H2020-LC-GD-2020 / H2020-LC-GD-2020-1), Part B, p. 4.

et al., 2002) adversely affecting key sectors such as livestock, agriculture and tourism (NNF, 2016; Shikangalah & Mapani, 2020, DECOSA, 2016). Data of 2019, indicate that in **South Africa** about 7.5 million hectare of land (around 6%) have been affected by woody biomass overgrowth (DEA, 2019; Warren et al., 2018) affecting the agricultural productivity and biodiversity of 10-20 million hectare of the country's productive land (DEA, 2019, O'Connor et al., 2014). In **Botswana**, data regarding unwanted woody biomass overgrowth is less extensive than in Namibia and South Africa, however, reports of 1980 indicated that approx. 25% of the rangeland was affected through rangeland degradation (Vanderpost et al., 2011). In 1994, already 37,000 km² (6.4%) of the land was affected by the encroachment of woody vegetation (Vetter, 2005, Moleele et al., 2002, Botswana Government, 1975; Tsimako, 1991). Data of 2002, reported that woody biomass overgrowth had degraded over 4 million ha.² Even though Botswana is less studied in terms of unwanted woody biomass overgrowth, data shows that unwanted woody biomass overgrowth is progressively expanding.

2.1.1 CAUSES OF UNWANTED WOODY BIOMASS OVERGROWTH

Unwanted woody biomass overgrowth is more likely to develop in desert and mesic grasslands and Savannas, however, these ecosystems are not clearly defined (Naito & Cairns, 201; ZEF, 2016). Similar challenges surface when trying to define the drivers triggering unwanted woody biomass overgrowth. Evidence has shown that while one driver can be triggering woody biomass overgrowth within one ecosystem it might obstruct the process in another. Nonetheless, Savanna ecosystems are commonly between the most vulnerable to unwanted woody biomass overgrowth. For this ecosystem, increasing livestock, rainfall and soil moisture are key factors triggering unwanted woody biomass overgrowth. Fire occurrences also play an important role in Savanna ecosystems, since its absence is reported to lead to the expansion of woody vegetation, as well as increasing Co2 levels (Bond & Midgley, 2012; ZEF, 2016).

Woody biomass overgrowth can be driven by various factors, depending on the ecosystem and socio-economic context. Some general factors of unwanted woody biomass overgrowth are enlisted below.

- **Overgrazing:** Prolonged and high grazing pressure from herbivores inhibits the growth of grass layer and allows unwanted woody biomass to thrive (DEA, 2019, p. 4). It also results in less grass and limited fuel load for fire which controls overgrowth of unwanted woody biomass (Venter et al., 2018).

² Grant Agreement (Nr. 101036401 — SteamBioAfrica — H2020-LC-GD-2020 / H2020-LC-GD-2020-1), Part B, p. 4.

- **Suppression of natural savannah bush fires:** Regular burning of savannah ecosystems inhibits the growth and maturity of woody plants that are resistant to fire and not reachable by browsers (Mphinyane et al., 2011, Kgosikoma et al., 2012). Fire also allows new healthy and resilient grass to grow thus promoting a healthy competition between grass and woody plant populations (Ingwelala, 2015).
- **Changes in rainfall patterns:** Higher annual amounts and frequency of rainfall move savannas more towards closed forest systems whereas prolonged dry seasons result in decreased canopy cover and an increase in fire frequency thereby changing landscapes into grassland systems (Angassa & Oba, 2007, DEA, 2019, p. 4, DEA, 2019, p. 5, Joubert et al., 2008).
- **Soil characteristics:** A combination of low nutrient soil and high rainfall may result in increased unwanted woody biomass overgrowth (DEA, 2019, p. 4). Unwanted woody biomass is also likely to expand in sandy soil with low clay content (Kgosikoma et al., 2012), whereas increased nitrogen deposition in the soil may decrease the overgrowth of unwanted woody biomass (Sankaran et al., 2008).
- **Increase in CO₂ in the atmosphere:** An increase in atmospheric carbon dioxide helps C₃ plants (woody bushes) to grow faster and to outpace C₄ species (grasses) in savanna ecosystems leading progressively to unwanted woody biomass overgrowth (DEA, 2019, p. 4).
- **Prevention of natural migration of wild animals:** Browsers and grazers play a very important role in regulating the amount of woody vegetation cover (Hempson et al., 2017) that can make ecosystems either more or less vulnerable to unwanted woody biomass overgrowth (Augustine & McNaughton, 2004).
- **Climate Change:** Climate change affects savannah ecosystems through various factors such as increased levels of atmospheric carbon dioxide, temperatures, droughts, precipitation, and fire frequency (Jansson & Hofmockel, 2020), thereby influencing unwanted woody biomass overgrowth in one way or the other. Climate change is already happening in Southern Africa with, higher average temperatures, increasing frequency of droughts and reduced water availability (Kusangaya et al, 2014).

2.1.2 IMPACT OF UNWANTED WOODY BIOMASS OVERGROWTH

Unwanted woody biomass overgrowth has an important impact on the functioning of ecosystem services, which undermines food and water security and increases the vulnerability and livelihoods of surrounding communities. Some important negative impacts of unwanted woody biomass overgrowth include the loss of grazing capacity, decreased productivity in farmlands, depletion of groundwater reserves, and soil degradation. These impacts are further described below:

- **The loss of grazing capacity:** Rangelands are very essential for free-range livestock and game farming due to the importance of grasslands particularly for grazers. Grazing is one of the important economic ways of using rangelands particularly in communal or pastoral areas (Lesoil et al., 2013). Unwanted woody biomass overgrowth results in grasslands being displaced and replaced by woody elements over time thus lowering forage yield and quality. It causes extensive changes in land cover thereby diminishing and weakening the productivity of farmlands and rangelands. It increases the density of unpalatable shrubs and trees in savannah ecosystems and reduces their carrying capacity thus threatening the sustainability of grazing animal production in such ecosystems and the livelihoods of pastoral communities.

The higher bush density in rangelands reduces land accessibility by livestock and affects the biodiversity and nutrient cycling of the affected areas (Ayalew & Muluaem, 2018). Consequently, this can have significant economic consequences for livestock and game industries. A study looking at the Highveld and Drakensberg Grassland zone, in South Africa, for example, found that the encroachment of bankrupt bush on commercial rangelands decreased livestock production by about 65% (Avenant, 2015). The study further indicated that the majority of farmers in the study area had lost between 30–60% of their grazing land. Further, the same study reported that a total of 35% of the commercial farmland included in the survey had been affected (Avenant, 2015; DEA, 2019, p. 45). In Namibia, it is reported that unwanted woody biomass overgrowth has resulted in competition with vegetation that feeds livestock, and subsequently led to 1.4 - 1.6 billion N\$ (83.714.400 - 95.673.600 €) national financial loss (MAWF, 2012; NAU, 2010).

- **Decreased productivity in farmlands:** Unwanted woody biomass overgrowth causes extensive changes in land cover thereby diminishing and weakening the productivity of farmlands. The reduction in the carrying capacity of rangelands and farmlands threatens the livelihood of surrounding communities whose lives depend on the savanna landscapes. At its extreme

it leads to the displacement of smallholder farmers to live in poverty on the edge of townships. In the worst-case scenario, unwanted woody biomass overgrowth can also lead to the displacement of smallholder farmers to live in poverty on the edge of towns (Shikangalah & Mapani, 2020, p. 2). Unwanted woody biomass overgrowth has affected agriculture which is the main source of livelihood for many Namibians' affecting about 50% of 71 million hectares of commercial land and more than 15 million hectares of communal land (De Wet, 2015). This has significantly reduced the land productivity in Namibia in the recent years (Charis et al., 2019; De Klerk, 2004; MAWF, 2012; MITSMED, 2016; Temmerman, 2016) leading to lower food security and nutrition in communal farms (MAWF, 2012; NAU, 2010).

- **Loss in tourism appeal and value:** Savanna ecosystems are quite rich in fauna and are home to a wide variety of animal species ranging from carnivorous, herbivorous, omnivorous, to scavengers, etc. They are therefore very essential in the provision of nature-based tourism. Unwanted woody biomass overgrowth can change vegetation structure and increase its density in savannah landscapes thereby affecting the availability and diversity of animal species in them. It affects the wildlife habitat and forage production, depletes soil and water resources, and reduces plant and animal diversity in savannah ecosystems. As a result, this may decrease tourist satisfaction and the attractiveness of such areas. A study found out that the ease of spotting animals in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa, was significantly reduced when shrub cover exceeded about 30% due to reduced herd sizes and densities of animals (Arbieu et al., 2017). Moreover, studies have further indicated that an increase in vegetation height and density affected tourists' wildlife viewing experience making such protected areas unattractive for future potential tourists (Arbieu et al., 2017; Gray & Bond, 2013).
- **Depletion of groundwater reserves:** Unwanted woody biomass overgrowth interferes with hydrological services through increased evapotranspiration, decreased infiltration and decreased surface runoff. This threatens the already fragile water balance in arid and semi-arid regions of savannah ecosystems and leads to reductions in water supply. Consequently, this can easily lead to water and food insecurity in the surrounding communities. A study in South Africa indicated that unwanted woody biomass overgrowth can cause a loss of over 44 million litres/year/ha of groundwater through evapotranspiration due to proliferation of higher-biomass plants that reduce significantly the proportion of rainfall that ends up as stream flow or that infiltrates into groundwater (Christian & Associates, 2010; DEA, 2019, p. 4). Moreover, most

unwanted woody biomass has long tap root systems that enable them to intercept rainwater that should otherwise be available to other plants, animals or humans making them more vulnerable to drought. Shortage in groundwater supply can also further aggravate shortage of grass for livestock which can lead to a scarcity in animal feed available (Shikangalah & Mapani, 2020, p. 12).

- **Soil degradation:** Ground cover plays a significant role in controlling the rates of runoff and sediment loss in savanna landscapes (Bartley et al., 2006). Bush encroachment as a result of overgrazing leads to degradation of grassland and this results in soil damage and erosion (NNF, 2016; Shikangalah & Mapani, 2020). Moreover, trampling by livestock leads to soil compaction and this increases soil surface erosion, especially via water runoff. Despite the vegetative cover provided by bush encroachers, soil erosion and damage are still more likely to occur in situations of unwanted woody biomass overgrowth than under more natural conditions. However, it is also worth mentioning that some species protect the soil against soil erosion due to their strong root systems and bigger canopy. Moreover, leguminous bush encroachers enrich the soil with nitrogen and with leaf debris as they are deciduous (DECOSA, 2016).

Given the predominantly negative consequences associated with unwanted woody biomass overgrowth and its impact on farmland productivity and rural livelihoods, various methods have been proposed for avoiding, controlling or reversing unwanted woody biomass overgrowth. Active reduction of bush and restoration can reduce net Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions and enhance climate change resilience. However, at present there are **insufficient financial returns from harvesting this biomass to stimulate its large-scale removal**, e.g., the cost to clear this biomass overgrowth exceeds the immediate benefits of increased agricultural productivity (Seebauer et al., 2019). Thus, there is a pressing need to create increased value from harvested bush. The transformation of woody biomass into a sustainable and secure clean bioenergy supply, would not only increase the value of the harvested biomass through the production of biofuel, but also through the restoration of ecosystem services. In addition, it will address the region's energy needs and tackle other related pressing social and economic problems resulting from the progressive advance of native and invasive woody biomass in Southern Africa.

2.2 ACCESS TO ENERGY AND ENERGY POVERTY IN BOTSWANA, NAMIBIA AND SOUTH AFRICA

Botswana, Namibia and South Africa are members of Southern Africa Development Community (SADC). SADC covers eleven countries and has a total population of over 130 million people. Whilst the three countries are stable middle-income democracies, they suffer from some of the greatest income inequalities in the world. The GINI index shows values of inequality, in which a score of 1.0 indicates 'perfect inequality' and 0.0 indicates 'perfect equality'. The GINI score for South Africa is 0.632 (2014), for Botswana 0.533 (2015) and Namibia 0.591 (2015) (World Population Review, 2022). In 2022, the rural population is of about 30% in Botswana (World Population Review, 2022), around 49% in Namibia (World Population Review, 2022), and close to 33% in South Africa (World Bank 2020).

The World Energy 2020 Energy Trilemma Index (WEC, 2021) recognises the improvements made across Africa in energy access and efficiency. However, they are all still in the lower half of the global rankings. This index comparatively ranks 128 countries energy systems. Table 5 presents the scores for the three African countries participant in this project. This highlights **a need to substantially improve these three countries' energy security.**

Country	Score	Security	Equity	Sustainability	Population (in millions)	Area / sq km
Botswana	59.2	98	79	68	2.3	566.7 k
Namibia	58.3	95	90	23	2.5	822.3 k
South Africa	62.1	73	69	83	56.7	1213.1 k

Table 5 Scores for Botswana, Namibia and South Africa in the World Energy Trilemma Index 2020

Energy security is a complex and evolving concept (Trollip et al., 2014) and is defined as the uninterrupted availability of energy sources at an affordable price (IEA, n.d.). On the other hand, energy poverty is the lack of access to modern sources of energy (Zulu & Richardson, 2013) driven by both social and economic factors such as rising electricity prices, household incomes, and energy inefficient homes etc (SEA, 2017, p. 11, DoE, 2013). For instance, if the amount of energy that a household uses for lighting, or cooking or heating is reported as being less than adequate for its needs this is also considered energy poverty (DoE, 2013).

The prosperity and stability of any country depends largely on the availability of stable, abundant and affordable supply of energy. This includes reliable and efficient lighting, heating, cooking, mechanical power, transport, and telecommunication services. The availability and access to modern and high-quality, reliable and affordable energy contributes to better health and higher incomes, and to all-round improvements in the quality of life while also contributing to local and national development (Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung and the Authors, 2016, Zulu & Richardson, 2013). Access to affordable and reliable energy services is fundamental to reducing poverty and improving health, increasing productivity, enhancing competitiveness, and promoting economic growth (Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung and the Authors, 2016). For many sub-Saharan Africa countries increase in energy prices has resulted in higher and alarming unemployment rates (Ruppel & Althusmann, 2016).

At present the primary grid connected power supply is generated by polluting coal power plants in South Africa that are nearing the end of their operating life. This coal power supply needs to be replaced with one that is more sustainable and does not require major capital investment. Whilst grid access in South Africa is the highest in Africa (81%), it uses an ageing network transmission infrastructure, resulting in frequent and prolonged blackouts. Industry and many households that can afford the expense, now rely on their own power generators, which are coal or diesel powered. Grid connection, predominantly in prosperous urban areas, is lower in Namibia (53%) and Botswana (60%) (REN21, 2018).

The challenges faced in each country are detailed further in the country specific sections below.

2.2.1 BOTSWANA

Botswana is an arid to semi-arid country with a territory of about 600,000 square kilometres and a population of 2.3 million people of which 30% is located in rural areas. Nationwide the access to electricity in Botswana stands at 65%. In urban areas the access to electricity reaches 72% whereas in rural areas it only reaches 57%. The country has a highly inefficient system of transmission and distribution of electricity particularly to remote locations. This results in immense electric power losses (Bader, 2019). Estimations of the Department of Energy Botswana (Bader, 2019) indicate that in 2030 around 200,000 households will still have no access to electricity and about 300,000 households will have no access to clean energy sources for cooking. In addition, only 18% of the population will have access to clean energy for heating.

Figure 1 Electricity consumption by sector

Source: Statistics Botswana 2018 in Bader 2019

Botswana’s primary energy supply is predominantly fossil-based and heavily reliant on oil products and coal, complemented by biomass and waste energy (IRENA, 2021). In 2017 the country had a total energy supply of 2.9 Mtoe which consisted of oil products (35%), coal (44%), (traditional) biofuels and waste (19%) and imported electricity (2%) (IRENA, 2021). 82% of its installed domestic electricity capacity comes from coal. The country has vast reserves of coal estimated at about 40 Gt (IEA, 2013). In the past the country has experienced deficits in electricity generation due to technical limitations and challenges (Bader, 2019). As a result of the unreliable supply and to tackle the growing electricity demand, Botswana imports energy from the Southern Africa Power Pool (SAPP) – which comes mainly from South Africa (IRENA, 2021).

The country also generates a substantial amount of its electricity from imported refined petroleum products mainly from South Africa and Zambia that it uses to run its thermal power stations (REEEP, 2014). This poses a threat to the country’s future energy security. Limited supply routes as well as insufficient internal strategic storage capacity and huge travel distances required to supply the entire country leads to intermittent shortages in fuel supply. Thus, one of Botswana’s main policy objectives is to improve its energy supply to promote energy security (REEEP, 2014). Biomass wood fuel accounts for approx. 28% of Botswana’s primary energy supply (IRENA, 2021) and 38% of the total final energy consumption. Biomass wood fuel

is the main source of energy for a majority of the rural households in Botswana. On average, biomass supplies 46 per cent household energy nationally but this increases to as much as 77 % in rural areas (Nachmany et al., 2015).

Botswana's vast domestic energy resources present immense opportunities that can help the country in addressing its energy insecurities and increasing its access to energy services. The country also possesses considerable renewable energy potential including solar, wind and bioenergy that remain largely untapped (IRENA, 2021). Botswana has set a target of ensuring that at least 15% of the energy mix by 2030 is from renewable energy (IRENA, 2021).

Cooking and heating energy sources

About 71% and 42% of the population in Botswana rely on liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) and wood fuel respectively as their main energy sources for cooking (IRENA, 2021). LPG is used mostly in the urban areas and wood fuel in the urban

Botswana's primary energy supply is predominantly fossil-based and heavily reliant on oil products and coal

areas. In 2009, a wood fuel usage rate of 53% in rural and 13.1% in urban households was reported (SEforALL, 2012). 75% of households also use wood alongside their modern-fuel stoves (Hiemstra-van der Horst & Hovorka, 2008; SEforALL, 2012). About 41% of the rural population use LPG alongside wood fuel. Even though firewood is mostly used by households, other sectors such as education, health and manufacturing industries also use it for cooking purposes.

Commercial availability of improved stoves in Botswana is still low (SEforALL, 2012). Generally, the use of firewood has been declining over the years in Botswana as a result of increased access to and influence of electricity (CSO, 2012).

The use of electricity by households is still very low with only 1% of rural households and 3% of urban poor households reported to be using it as their principal energy source for cooking (SEforALL, 2016).

Challenges of popular cooking and heating energy sources in Botswana

Even though most parts of Botswana have access to electricity, the uptake of electricity varies significantly depending on the settlement size and the income group. In many rural areas, especially remote and small towns, connection rates tend to be extremely low, mostly because households cannot afford the high connection costs and tariffs (Agarwal et al., 2018). Thus, cost is one of the most important challenges hindering the access to electricity in rural Botswana.

In Botswana, firewood is mostly used for cooking, heating water and spaces, and in some cases lighting. In past decades, population growth in Botswana has led to the expansion of poverty levels, increased low-income groups and triggered rural-urban migration. All of this, has exerted a constant increase in demand for firewood. Thus, given the patterns of economic growth in rural areas, firewood will continue to remain the staple fuel for the upcoming years, unless alternative cooking and heating energy sources are made available, reliable and affordable to low- and middle-income groups. However, firewood usage results in depletion of wood resources due higher harvesting rates of the resources than nature can replenish. This leads to significant decline in the density and amount of vegetation and wildlife. This situation is further aggravated by the fact that the Botswana government has very limited capacity to monitor and manage wood resources (Mphinyane et al., 2018).

Problems associated with firewood collection include the hardship of collecting natural firewood from increasing distances from the villages and in some instances the interference caused by erratic weather during the time of collection (Mphinyane et al., 2018). Decline in the density and amount of vegetation near villages due to environmental degradation affects firewood availability and affordability. Collection of firewood is also mainly the responsibility of women and children except for when donkey-carts or vans are used, when men are also often involved. With the depletion of wood resources in areas closest to homesteads, more time is spent in firewood collection thus depriving children of study-time and women of other productive chores such as commercial activities, adult education, or participating in village governance structures.

The cutting down of trees to convert it into woody biomass resources such as firewood and charcoal results in deforestation (Hood, 2010) which in turn leads to an increase in greenhouse gas emissions and a consequent acceleration of climate change impacts. A continued rise in prices of firewood as a result of declining amounts makes firewood more and more expensive and out of the reach of many households, particularly low-income households. The only way to tackle this issue is through the substitution of firewood with other energy sources. In urban areas and large villages, the switch to paraffin, gas or electricity may be feasible, however, it might be more difficult for the rural population living in remote areas with neither the national grid nor adequate distribution networks for the other cooking and heating energy sources (Agarwal et al., 2018).

2.2.2 NAMIBIA

Namibia has a surface area of 824,290 square kilometres and is one of the least densely populated countries in Sub-Saharan Africa. The population and Housing Census data of 2015 showed that Namibia had 2.5 million inhabitants and 465,000 households, of which 58% live in rural and 42% urban areas (Helbig & Nuulimba, 2016). The country has one of the lowest population densities in sub-Saharan Africa of 2.6 persons per square kilometre (NSA, 2011).

Providing electricity access to its 79% rural population remains Namibia's main challenge

The primary energy sources in Namibia include liquid fossil fuels (diesel, petrol, paraffin, liquid petroleum gas and related energy carriers); biomass (wood and processed wood products and charcoal); and, to a lesser extent, coal. Electricity, either imported or generated locally, is Namibia's main source of secondary energy. The country imports 100% of its oil and gas requirements, and more than 60% of its electricity demand especially from South Africa (Ruppel & Althusmann, 2016). Most of its locally generated electricity is from hydro-power but it also has a small but growing proportion of electricity produced from solar energy (Von Oertzen, 2015).

Encroacher bush is also used to produce energy in the country (Danish Energy Management & Esbensen, 2017). Namibia's dominant economic sectors such as mining and agriculture are highly energy dependent. Despite its low population density Namibia has a very high domestic energy use making it a very energy intensive country (Von Oertzen, 2015).

Namibia's grid connection in 2019 stood at 53% covering mostly the urban areas. About 1 million Namibian households are still without access to electricity (CIA, 2019). Servicing the low population density spread over long distances and with a comparatively insignificant electrical load proves to be quite a challenge for grid extension in the country.

The country's high reliance on imports of fuels, consumer goods and manufactured products affects its ability to eradicate poverty and grow the economy (Von Oertzen, 2015). Providing electricity access to its 79% rural and sparse population that lack access particularly through feasible and maintainable off-grid solutions remains Namibia's main challenge (REN21, 2018).

According to World Energy Outlook, by 2030, 36% of Namibians will still not have access to modern energy under the business-as-usual scenario, 32% will have access to the grid, 11% to a mini-grid and 22% to a Solar Home System (SHS) (World Energy Outlook Report, 2019).

Namibia possesses considerable potential of untapped opportunities for renewable energy generation, investment, development and expansion. For instance, the country has a daily solar radiation of 6 kWh/m², with its solar regime being one of the best globally (Meteonorm, 2009) and it holds a huge development potential. In addition, the country has numerous on-shore wind energy sites, great biomass potential particularly from unwanted woody biomass (von Oertzen, 2012), a very high hydro-electric potential, a geothermal potential estimated to exceed 100 MW, as well as tidal and wave energy potentials of more than 200 MW that are considered realistic (von Oertzen, 2012).

Cooking and heating energy sources in Namibia

Namibia relies heavily on firewood. It is estimated that 53% and 46% of Namibian households use firewood for cooking and heating respectively (Helbig & Nuulimba, 2016). Firewood is a particular dominant energy source in rural areas. Approximately 86% of rural households use firewood compared to only 20% of urban households (NSA, 2011; Von Oertzen, 2015). Despite the challenges related to firewood (see table 6) a recent study shows that a majority of the rural households in Namibia will continue relying on traditional cooking energy sources in the foreseeable future (MME, 2017).

Strengths

- High acceptance as cooking and heating material
- Cost free energy source for most of the rural population
- Labour intensive; no skills required
- Very low investment
- No additional inputs (e.g. water, electricity) required
- High local demand
- High value addition if marketed in urban centres

Challenges

- Hardly any formal value chain
- Limited value addition and income generation of the producers
- High prices for end-consumers who have to purchase firewood
- Low energy efficiency
- increasing demand of low income groups in informal settlements of urban centres

Table 6 Strengths and challenges of firewood as energy source in Namibia

Source: adapted from (DECOSA, 2015)

It is estimated that slightly more 440,000 tons of firewood is harvested for own use in Namibia (Rothauge, 2014). **Households mostly collect the firewood for their own use** by themselves or they purchase it. About 30% of the households purchase the firewood from a seller, whereas roughly 10% purchase it from a supermarket (Helbig & Nuulimba, 2016). A report estimated that more than

120,000 tonnes of the firewood produced for own use is from unwanted woody biomass alone (DAS, 2020). On average, a household consumes about 8 kg of firewood (Helbig & Nuulimba, 2016).

Electricity is the second-most used energy source for cooking with almost 33% of all households nationally using it for cooking. 75% of these are urban households whereas about 7% are rural households (NSA, 2011; Von Oertzen, 2015). In the urban areas both wood and electricity are available and have to be purchased. Only approx. 8% of Namibians use liquid petroleum gas (LPG) for cooking, a majority of them being in the urban areas.

The **charcoal industry** in Namibia is well developed and highly commercialised with most of the charcoal it produces destined for the **export market**. Namibia produces about 12,000 tonnes of charcoal annually, most of which is exported. The country is among the **top ten charcoal exporters globally** and ranked fifth worldwide in 2015 (MITSMED, 2016). However, only a small proportion of the charcoal produced in Namibia is intended for domestic consumption with the local demand not being more than 1,000 tonne p.a. Though the consumption seemed to increase slightly, barbeque in Namibia was still dominated by firewood. The charcoal industry is one of the largest employment sectors in the country's economy (FAO, 2020). In the country, charcoal and charcoal briquettes are predominantly used in the urban areas.

Challenges of popular cooking and heating energy sources in Namibia

Namibia relies heavily on traditional biomass for cooking and space heating a trend that is likely to continue in the foreseeable future (SEforALL, 2016). This situation needs to be improved particularly through energy efficient technologies and the deployment of modern forms of energy in order to address the increasing deforestation in large parts of Namibia as a result of the overreliance on traditional biomass.

There are environmental implications associated with exploitation of natural vegetation for firewood and charcoal for both domestic and commercial usage. For instance, overexploitation of woodland resources within agricultural landscapes exerts pressure on the natural vegetation, culminating in soil erosion and silting of water bodies. Furthermore, exploitation of forest resources as a source of energy both for commercial or domestic usage results in deforestation, depletion of soil fertility, land degradation, desertification, especially in arid and semi-arid areas.

Energy affordability is a critical issue in Namibia particularly due to low incomes and inefficient and costly forms of energy supply. In addition, 63% and 65% of net energy (for example liquid fuels) and electricity consumed in Namibia respectively is imported. This results in high cost and unreliability of energy supplies which impacts industrial development, employment generation, poverty alleviation and public health.

2.2.3 SOUTH AFRICA

The Republic of South Africa (RSA) is one of the most industrialised countries and the third-largest economy in Africa. It is the highest primary energy consumer on the continent (IRENA, 2020). In 2020 the majority of RSA's total population (over 67%) lived in urban areas and cities and just 33% lived in rural areas making the country (Statista, 2022).

South Africa is heavily reliant on coal for meeting its energy needs. However, it is making efforts to diversify its power mix by introducing natural gas and renewables due to its ageing coal-fired fleet (IEA, 2019). Coal constitutes about 67% of the country's total primary energy supply (IRENA, 2020), oil (16%), petroleum products (6.8%), nuclear (3.5%) and natural gas (2.2%). However, recent gas discoveries could change this and reduce its import needs (IEA, 2019; IRENA, 2020).

In 2015 the country's total electricity production amounted to 272.2 terawatt hours (TWh) with coal accounting for over 85% of the mix, nuclear (5.4%) and hydro (1.8%) (IRENA, 2020). RSA has a well-developed, but ageing and increasingly unreliable, electricity network and one of the highest electricity access rates (85%) of modern energy access in SSA, far higher than the 49% access rate of the Southern Africa region (IRENA & AfDB, 2022). South Africa also has the highest grid access (81%), in Africa. 87% of the country's households have access to electricity (SEA, 2014), while 47% are considered energy poor (DoE, 2013a).

RSA uses an ageing network transmission infrastructure that results in frequent and prolonged blackouts. This has forced many industries and households, particularly those who can afford it, to resort to using their own power generators powered by either coal or diesel. Rural South African households who still live below the poverty line and are resource poor mostly rely on traditional energy sources such as cutting and fetching fuelwood from forest to meet their energy needs (Practical Action, 2014).

The country has a very high wind power potential (estimated to be 6,7000 GW,) and solar power potential (Jain & Jain, 2017) as well as excellent natural resources for CSP development (IEA, 2019). At 2,500 hours of sunshine per year, and 4.5 to 6.6 kWh/ m2 of radiation level, among the top three in the world. In order to tap its renewable energy sources, the country has developed ambitious plans for gradually reducing its overreliance on coal and has successfully scaled up national renewables-based generation at a competitive cost, driven by the Renewable Energy Independent Power Producer Programme (IRENA, 2020).

Cooking and heating energy sources in South Africa

RSA has 86% access to clean cooking (IRENA & AfDB, 2022) and accounts for 73% of the electric cooking households in Sub-Saharan Africa (World Bank, 2014). The majority of its households (77%) use electricity as their main energy source for cooking (IRENA, 2020) including many low-income households who own electric stoves. However, most low-income households still use solid fuels to supplement electricity. According to DoE, 40% of households across RSA are using multiple fuels for cooking (DoE, 2013b, CCSA, 2017, p. 196). Only a few households (10%) depend on fuelwood, particularly those in rural areas (IEA, 2019).

Other energy sources for cooking used in South African households include gas (5%), paraffin (4%), solar electricity (3%) and coal (1%) (CCSA, 2017, p. 196). Only a few households in South Africa continue to rely on fuelwood (6%) or gas (5%) once they have been connected to electricity. Firewood (54%) and paraffin (38%) are the dominant energy sources for cooking in the RSA households that are not connected to electricity (CCSA, 2017, p. 196).

Most RSA electrified households (41%) use electricity for space heating. The use of other energy sources for space heating, including coal and gas is still very low and stands at 5% (CCSA, 2017, p. 196). However, non-electrified households, rely mostly on firewood for space heating, used by 29% of the households, followed by paraffin (11%), and coal (5%) (DoE, 2013).

Challenges of popular cooking and heating energy sources in South Africa

In low-income communities, non-electric fuel sources are usually associated with Household Air Pollution (HAP) (Rehfuess et al., 2014).

In RSA, about 20% of households were exposed to indoor smoke from burning of solid fuels causing 2489 deaths in the country in the year 2000 a figure that has so far doubled according to latest Global Burden of Disease study with most of the disease burden reported among Black African households (Stanaway et al., 2018).

Exposure to HAP from solid fuel burning is also a pressing public health problem in the country, particularly in low-income communities (Bruce et al., 2015). For instance, low-cost coal is readily available and used by low-income communities for cooking and heating purposes in the interior of RSA, especially near coal mines and coal-fired power stations (Language et al., 2016) exposing them to the dangers and risks associated with HAP. In such areas, electricity is only used for lighting purposes.

The effects of exposure to indoor air pollution as a result of using wood, paraffin or coal for heating and/or cooking particularly among poor or low-income households in RSA is further exacerbated by other factors such as poor ventilation in the dwelling, inefficient stoves, smoking and burning of incense and mosquito repellent, indoor temperature and relative humidity levels (Naicker et al., 2017; Norman et al., 2007).

Paraffin is also used for cooking and heating in coastal regions of RSA with limited availability of wood and coal (Muller et al., 2003). Fumes resulting from burning paraffin have been found to cause Lower Respiratory Tract Infections (LRTIs) such as pneumonia and bronchiolitis (Muller et al., 2003).

In terms of the **cooking and heating energy sources** firewood plays a central role in most of the rural households in the three southern African countries though with varying degrees. Whereas in Botswana and Namibia fuelwood is the predominant source of energy used for cooking and heating in the rural areas with more than two thirds of the rural population using relying on it as their main source of energy, in the South Africa the proportion of households that depend on firewood as their main source of energy is way lower, however, for the households that are not connected to electricity it is still the dominant source of energy. Other than the rural or urban setting, the use of fuelwood in the three countries is also influenced by the socio-economic status with many low-income households using it mainly for cooking and also for heating.

Based on the trends in South Africa and Namibia it can be assumed that households that have access to electricity prefer to use it as their main source of energy for cooking and heating. Taking South Africa as an example, the country has one of the highest electricity access rates with most of the rural and urban households connected to the electricity grid. As a result, a majority of the households mainly use electricity. The data from desktop research even revealed that the minute households in South Africa were connected to electricity they preferred to use it for cooking compared to other energy sources. Looking at Namibia, it is noteworthy that though the electricity access rates for households

Households that have access to electricity prefer to use it as their main source of energy for cooking and heating

in Namibia is still very low compared to South Africa, the majority of the urban households in the country that are connected to the electricity grid use it as their main source of energy for cooking and heating. With regards to the use of electricity, Botswana presents a totally different picture given the fact that LPG is the dominant cooking and heating energy source even in households that have access to electricity. Despite over two thirds of the population in Botswana having access to electricity, its use for cooking and heating purposes is still very low in both rural and urban settings in the country. It can be assumed that this is influenced by other factors such as the electricity infrastructure and reliability, the price of electricity compared to gas among other factors. However, it is worth mentioning that though LPG (i.e., propane, butane, or a mix of the two) is already the most utilised alternative to solid biomass for cooking in Sub Saharan Africa (IEA, 2017), its uptake is still very low mainly due to the fact that its accessibility still remains highly problematic. The distribution of LPG from production sites or import stations to the single users requires the careful handling, storage, and transport of pressurised gas which is quite complicated.

The current **access to energy and energy poverty** varies in the three countries. RSA boasts of the very highest electricity access rates compared to Botswana and Namibia. As a result, both Botswana and Namibia rely on electricity imports especially from RSA to meet their domestic energy demands. Moreover, Botswana and Namibia also rely on fuel imports particularly of oil and gas to meet their domestic requirements. Both South RSA and Botswana rely heavily on coal to meet their energy needs.

In terms of their electricity transmission infrastructure, all the three countries experience inefficiencies and challenges in the transmission and distribution of electricity to remote locations resulting in the power supply being either insufficient or unreliable. This is mainly due to factors such as poor maintenance of infrastructure, lack of reliable fuel supply and insufficient transmission and distribution capacity etc. Energy affordability is a critical issue in all the three countries and is a major challenge particularly for poor and low-income households that are forced to spend a substantial amount of their income on energy. As a result, most of the rural and poor households' resort to using traditional forms of energy such as fuelwood which they gather or collect by themselves.

The main **challenges associated with popular cooking and heating energy** sources in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa are linked to non-electric fuel sources, particularly solid fuels such as firewood, charcoal and coal that are used mainly among low-income families or poor families. The challenges that cut across the three countries include health-related complications or even death as a result of HAP; environmental implications associated with overexploitation of natural vegetation (e.g., woodland resources) that leads to deforestation, soil degradation, climate change among other challenges; time related challenges due to the amount of time that either women or children have to spend it collecting the fuelwood which robs them of the time that they would otherwise use to engage in other productive activities.

The value chains of charcoal and firewood present similar characteristics to the proposed solid biofuel. This offers great potential for the project to build the value chain of the solid biofuel on the existing chains. The mapping and analysis of the two value chains have shed lights into some gaps and opportunities that the project can address in the commercialization of the new solid biofuel.

3.1 EXISTING VALUE CHAINS OF COOKING AND HEATING ENERGY SOURCES IN BOTSWANA, NAMIBIA AND SOUTH AFRICA

3.1.1 BOTSWANA

Cooking and heating energy sources

According to results of the baseline survey, in Botswana the type of energy sources used for cooking and heating vary according to locations. In urban Botswana, 69% of respondents used an energy mix. This consists of electricity plus multiple additional sources, commonly LPG, then firewood. In **urban** areas, charcoal and firewood generally are not used for everyday cooking and heating but rather for social activities and entertainment on weekends and holidays, for grilling, barbecuing or lighting bonfires. In **peri-urban** areas, 68% of respondents also combined the use of electricity with firewood or LPG. Respondents that did not report on using multiple energy sources generally used electricity. In **rural** areas, the situation looked similar with 80% of respondents reporting on the use of several energy sources. This consists of electricity and firewood or LPG. Respondents that did not report on using energy mix generally used electricity as their main energy source.

Figure 2 Charcoal and firewood usage in Botswana by location (%)

In terms of charcoal and firewood consumption for cooking and heating, Figure 2 shows how populations in urban, peri-urban and rural areas of Botswana have a different preference, as found out in the SBA project’s 2022 baseline survey. This finding confirms a relatively high charcoal consumption in urban areas for leisure activities, and lower charcoal consumption in peri-urban and rural areas.

In contrast, firewood consumption is substantially higher in the peri-urban and rural areas, though this type of energy source is also popular in urban areas most likely due to its affordability (Mphinyane et al., 2018).

Commercialisation of charcoal and firewood

To a large extent, the **charcoal** consumed in Botswana is imported from South Africa and Namibia. Importing firms sell charcoal which they buy from Namibia and South Africa through distribution centres to wholesalers and supermarkets. However, the local production of charcoal is taking off recently. **Community based organisations (CBOs)** in Botswana work with local communities to produce charcoal as a way to create new income streams for communities. CBO producers sell charcoal to bulk buyers such as wholesalers, supermarkets, gas stations, but also directly to household consumers. Other small local producers sell charcoal that they produce to bulk buyers and small retail shops. Wholesalers sell charcoal mostly to supermarkets, gas stations and small retail shops. Locally-produced charcoal is slightly more expensive than the imported charcoal. In general, gas stations tend to charge higher price for charcoal, followed by supermarkets and then wholesalers. In the past, even though wholesalers were only allowed to sell to customers with a permit, nowadays they can sell to anyone and offer a relatively competitive price.

In the baseline survey, both wholesalers and small-scale retailers, i.e., shops, kiosks and open-air stalls, reported that the demand of charcoal in Botswana is relatively stable throughout the year. This indicates that charcoal demand does not represent a challenge. However, **wholesalers** in Gaborone, the capital city of Botswana, reported some key challenges to charcoal commercialisation (sales) in urban areas. These include **unreliable supply** and **low availability**. The **small-scale retailers** (shops, kiosks and open-air stall) in and around Gaborone (i.e., urban and peri-urban areas), reported on similar challenges in charcoal sales, which include **high cost** and **low accessibility**. These are likely contributed by a large distance to access bigger retailers and/or poor road infrastructure.

The commercialisation of **firewood** is significantly different from charcoal. In Botswana, collecting firewood for commercial purposes requires a permit. Independent commercial wood cutters sell their firewood at outlets along the A1 Road which connects Northern and Southern Botswana. Firewood outlets sell products using donkey carts and target mostly rural and peri-urban consumers. In addition, wood cutters use the social media (mainly Facebook) to sell their firewood directly to household consumers in the peri-urban and urban areas. This type of

small online sellers has drastically increased in number in the past two years of the COVID-19 pandemic. In rural areas, however, it is very common that household consumers go out, cut and collect firewood themselves for their own consumption.

Wholesalers and small-scale retailers, shops, kiosks and open-air stalls

In Botswana, the commercialisation of charcoal and firewood mainly involves two groups of actors, which are a) wholesalers and b) small-scale retailers (supermarkets, petrol stations), kiosks and open-air stalls.

Wholesalers

There were 13 respondents from wholesalers participated in the project's baseline survey, where the majority were men (12 persons) with only one woman participating.

Regarding **gender distribution of employees**, most respondents indicated that more than half of the workforce are male. About 92% of the respondents are located in urban area (Gaborone) and only 8% in peri-urban area (Mogoditshane). Most businesses are owned by two or more persons. The respondents indicate that 83% of employees are permanent workers with only 17% seasonal workers.

During the survey with wholesalers, it was found out that customer demand is particularly high for charcoal and firewood. The wholesalers offer firewood usually in a **bundle** and charcoal in a **package**. The reason they sell firewood is because of its **favourable supply price** and **good quality**; while charcoal because of its **favourable supply price, reliable supply** and because it is safe to **handle and store**. On the other hand, customers make their buying decisions of energy source based on several factors, such as whether a product is **convenient or practical to use, affordable price** and **accessibility**.

Almost 70% of the wholesalers reported on experiencing price fluctuations of energy sources for cooking and heating in the past few years. They linked these fluctuations to **import tariffs, value added tax (VAT)** and **government levy**. In addition, 62% of the wholesalers reported on how their businesses were affected by the COVID-19 pandemic through **low customer demand**. About 53% of wholesaler respondents reported that they were affected by **increased prices** of cooking and heating energy sources.

Customers of the small-scale businesses tend to choose their cooking and heating energy sources for factors such as affordable price, practicality and convenience of use.

Furthermore, wholesalers reported that customers purchase different energy sources for cooking and heating **directly at their shop or warehouse**. However, a small number of customers also make orders **by phone**. Around 38% of the surveyed wholesalers offer **same day delivery services** to their customers, which makes it convenient for the customers to get their orders quickly.

Main customers of the surveyed wholesalers are **local businesses** and **local resellers and retailers**. However, more than a third of the wholesalers reported selling their products to international customers. The wholesaler respondents indicated that they received orders from both male and female contacts in equal numbers. The most common payment methods used by customers include **card payments**, which were offered by 100% of the surveyed wholesalers, and **cash up front**, offered by 92% wholesalers.

Small-scale retailers (supermarkets, petrol stations), kiosks and open-air stalls
In the baseline survey, 48 representatives from **small-scale retailers (supermarkets, petrol stations), kiosks and open-air stalls** participated. In most cases, they were managers or owners of supermarkets and petrol stations, where approximately 54% were men and 46% women. Regarding **gender distribution of employees** at workplace, most respondents indicated that all or more than half are male. About 37% of the respondents are located in **urban areas** (Gaborone, Phakalane) and 19% in **peri-urban areas** (Metismotlhaba, Mogoditshane, Tlokweng) and 44% in rural areas (Gabane, Mochudi, Ramotswa). Most shops were located at **shopping centres or along roadsides**, and only some in the local market. A big majority of respondents owned more than one shop, some even owned up to 40 shops.

The survey reveals that energy sources for cooking and heating with a highest customer demand include charcoal and firewood. The small-scale businesses base their decisions to sell different types of energy sources on several factors. They sell **firewood** due to **convenient access** to suppliers and **charcoal** due to **high demand, reliable supply** and its characteristic, that is **easy to handle and store**. Customers of the small-scale businesses tend to choose their cooking and heating energy sources for factors such as **affordable price, practicality and convenience** of use. In addition, product **accessibility** plays an important role in customer's decision making. The small-scale retailers, shops, kiosks and open-air stalls reported some impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic to their businesses. These include **low customer demand, increased prices** and **unreliable supply of products**.

All respondents indicated that their customers tend to buy energy sources directly from shops, kiosks, or stalls, only a small number of businesses (around 15% of respondents) offer delivery services to their customers. Most of the respondents reported that a delivery service can take **more than a week** and only a few respondents deliver **within a few hours**. About 82% of the respondents indicated that the **price** of cooking and heating energy sources had **changed in the past year (2021)**. They believed the price change was a result of an **increasing demand** of energy sources, taxes and increased supply costs.

The majority of customers of small-scale retailers, shops, kiosks and open-air stalls are **households**, followed by **local businesses**. The small-scale businesses also reported on doing business with both genders, male and female, in similar number when selling to households and other local businesses as well as buying products from other shops. Around 37% of the respondents sold cooking and heating energy sources to international customers, mostly in South Africa.

Brands and labels

More than 85% of the surveyed wholesalers and small-scale retailers (shops, supermarkets, petrol stations and open-air stalls) sold branded charcoal. For **wholesalers**, popular charcoal brands in Botswana include Namib, Kalahari, Hardwood Lump, Family Favourite. For **small-scale retailers**, the popular brands are Namib, Charka and Chesa. The respondents indicated that these brands were particularly popular because of **fair market price** and **reliable supply**. About 54% of the wholesalers reported that **brands are important**, while 77% of the small-scale retailers reported the same. Both wholesalers and small-scale retailers indicated that **brands are relevant for their customers** (61% and 79% of respondents respectively).

*Figure 4 Kalahari charcoal displayed in a shop in Botswana
Photos by BITRI*

Figure 3 Namib charcoal displayed in a shop in Botswana

Supply chain

Most of the surveyed **wholesalers** reported of having up to **four different suppliers** of cooking and heating energy sources. However, when it comes to **firewood and charcoal**, the wholesalers have only **one and two suppliers** (respectively). On the other hand, the **small-scale retailers** tend to have **one to three suppliers**.

It was found out that the wholesalers found their suppliers through advertisement. Similarly, the small-scale retailers found their suppliers through advertisement, but also through personal approach. The suppliers approach small-scale retailers and offer their products directly. The wholesalers and small-scale retailers indicated that they order the products **by phone** to the suppliers (61% and 58% of the respondents respectively). Only in a few exceptional cases wholesalers contacted suppliers through their **websites**.

The location of suppliers that serve the wholesalers varies greatly. **The suppliers can be located in the same area, in town or city or in other parts of the country.** In the case of small-scale retailers, their suppliers are generally located within the country. This means, their distance to the suppliers does not play a big role in selecting supplier as long as the product of interest can be accessed. Factors that do play a role when choosing suppliers are **good prices, convenient location (accessibility), reliable supply** and **good quality products**. It was found out that most of the surveyed wholesalers and small-scale retailer have no problem sourcing their products throughout the year (46% and 50% of respondents respectively). However, during winter time the supply can be affected, which results in shortages.

Price and packaging

The price of both firewood and charcoal shows strong variations depending on the brand, location (urban, peri-urban and rural) and type of vendor. The locally-produced charcoal is slightly more expensive than the imported brands, for example. Charcoal is more expensive in gas stations, and slightly cheaper at supermarkets and the cheapest is at wholesalers (where customers tend to buy in bulk quantity). In addition, the prices of firewood and charcoal have increased since the outbreak of COVID-19. Table 7 and Figure 5 (below) illustrate the **price variations** of charcoal and firewood in Botswana. Respondents (wholesalers and small-scale retailers) indicated that the price of firewood had increased from **20 BWP (1,57 €) to 30–35 BWP (2,36–2,75 €) for a package of 10 kg** in the pre-pandemic and during pandemic period. Similarly, the price of charcoal had increased from **19 - 45 BWP (1,49–3,54 €) to 30–70 BWP (2,36–5,50 €) for a package of 4kg** in the pre-pandemic and during pandemic period.

Energy source	Price before COVID-19	Price during COVID-19
Firewood (BWP per 10kg)	20	30-35
Charcoal (BWP per 4kg)	19-45	30-70

Table 7 Price of firewood and charcoal before and during the COVID-19 pandemic

*Figure 5 Firewood and charcoal displayed in a shop in Botswana
Photos by BITRI*

*Figure 6 Braaimeester and Namib charcoal displayed in a shop in Botswana
Photos by BITRI*

Challenges with existing cooking and heating energy sources

The survey found out, almost all wholesalers and small-scale retailers (92,3% and 91,6%of respondents respectively) were between **satisfied and very satisfied with the cooking and heating energy sources** they sold. However, they expressed a dissatisfaction with energy sources listed in Table 8. Factors affecting wholesalers’ satisfaction with **charcoal** include **expensive price, unreliable supply** and **bad quality**. On the other hand, the small-scale retailers reported factors such as **unreliable supply** and **too much competition**.

Energy source	Wholesalers	Small-scale retailers
LPG Gas	Unsafe to handle / store	Too expensive
Charcoal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Too expensive · Unreliable supply · Bad quality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Unreliable supply · Too much competition
Paraffin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Difficult to access · Bad quality 	
Firewood	Too expensive	Bad quality

Table 8 Reasons of dissatisfaction with the energy sources

In relation to **commercialisation** (sales) of cooking and heating energy sources, the wholesalers reported on **growing competition** from other wholesalers in the market as a challenge. On the other hand, **the small-scale retailers** reported as main challenges the **high pricing** of products, **lack of a commercialisation network** and continuous **changes in price**. In light of these challenges, both wholesalers and small-scale retailers, but particularly the latter, are open to new cooking and heating energy products that they can offer to the market.

Consumer preferences (households)

The baseline survey on household consumers in Botswana includes 99 respondents, of which 45.5% are male and 53.5% are female. Around 50% of the respondents are between 20 and 40 years old, 47% are heads of their household, and 56% have a university degree. Most household respondents are located in rural (39%) and urban areas (35%).

Location	Residential area	Percentage
Urban	Gaborone, Phakalane	35.4
Peri-urban	Metsimotlhaba, Mmopane, Mogoditshane, Tlokweng	25.2
Rural	Gabane, Mochudi, Ramotswa	39.4

Table 9 Geographical distribution of respondents

The living conditions of the household respondents are relatively good, 89% have **piped water**, and 68% have a **toilet flush system**. The most popular types of cooking facilities among respondents are gas stoves (available in 71% households), **electric stoves or hot plates** (available in 69% households) and an **outside fireplace** (available in 31% households). Accordingly, electricity (mentioned by 92% respondents), LPG (mentioned by 59% respondents) and firewood (mentioned by 44% respondents) are the most dominant energy sources for the households.

General factors influencing the households' decisions to choose energy sources are **efficiency of the product, suitable for all weather** and having a **reliable supply**. Hence, the most popular energy source for households is **electricity**. It is most commonly used for **cooking as well as water and space heating**. However, **LPG** is also an important energy source for **cooking**. This is followed by **firewood and charcoal**, which are used only for leisure activities such as barbecuing (Table 10).

Household activities	Most popular energy sources used
Cooking	Electricity and LPG gas
Space heating	Electricity
Water heating	Electricity
Barbecuing (Braaiing)	Firewood and charcoal

Table 10 Energy sources used for household activities

When buying cooking and heating energy sources, the surveyed households mentioned several factors influencing their buying decisions, which are **affordable price** (55% respondents) and **convenient and practical use** (33% respondents). The **least important factor** of consideration is whether an energy source is environmentally friendly.

More than **two thirds** of the respondents (69%) indicated that they **purchase** the cooking and heating energy sources, while **one third** (34%) indicated that they **purchase and collect** the energy sources they use, i.e., firewood. Most of the households purchase their cooking and heating energy sources (besides electricity) by visiting **supermarkets**. In regard to satisfaction with the chosen energy sources, only 40% of households were **satisfied**. The households reported **expensive cost of the energy sources** as the main factor of dissatisfaction.

Over 70% of the households indicated that they had heard about solid biofuels before. Mostly through advertisements on the **radio**, but also through the **social media** and **television**. However, half of the respondents (46%) indicated they have **never used solid biofuel before**. This is mostly due to lack of awareness of such products, but also because they use different energy sources. Almost all of the households said they are willing to test a new type of solid biofuel as part of the SteamBioAfrica project. However, only 8% would be willing to pay to test this new solid biofuel. Additionally, households reported that reasons to switch to a new type of solid biofuel for cooking and heating would be the **affordability of the product** and **product being environmentally friendly**.

3.1.2 NAMIBIA

Cooking and heating energy sources

According to results of the baseline survey, in Namibia the type of energy sources used for cooking and heating vary according to locations. In the **urban** areas, 50% of the respondents relied on a mix of energy. This mix consisted mostly of electricity and firewood, and sometimes LPG. Those, who did not use a mix of energy, usually simply rely on electricity alone. In the **peri-urban** areas, 72% of respondents used some sort of energy mix. This mostly consisted of a combination of electricity and firewood. In many cases LPG was also used. Those who did not use a mix of energy sources, mostly depended on electricity. In the **rural** areas of Namibia, 50% of respondents used a mix of energy, which did not include electricity but rather relied on a mix of firewood and “other” energy sources. The other 50%, who did not use a mix of energy, relied completely on firewood.

Commercialisation of charcoal and firewood

In Namibia charcoal is mostly used by household consumers in urban and peri-urban areas (see Figure 7). Rather than for daily cooking and heating, charcoal is particularly popular for leisure activities such as barbecuing. In rural areas, charcoal is not consumed. It is important to highlight that charcoal is an important export commodity for Namibia and the international demand on charcoal is an important driver of price increase and explains why charcoal

is mainly used for leisure activities in urban and peri-urban areas where higher income groups are located in contrast to rural areas. A report published by Namibia Ministry of Industrialisation, Trade and SME Development (MITSMED, 2016) reveals a very low domestic demand and consumption of charcoal, estimated at only 1,000 tonnes or less than 1% of current production. The report suggests that in Namibia charcoal is no longer the main domestic cooking fuel, but a symbol of an affluent lifestyle as it is mainly used for barbecues.

Figure 7 Charcoal and firewood usage in Namibia by location (%)

Firewood, on the other hand, is a highly popular energy source for daily cooking and heating in rural areas (see Figure 7). Many rural users collect firewood themselves, however some users in rural areas also buy firewood, usually in small amounts for daily use, which results expensive. In urban and peri-urban areas firewood is still relatively popular, especially for cooking traditional meals, but not for daily cooking and heating activities. These findings resonate with DECOSA (2015), which indicates that firewood is generally used by lower income groups, mainly for cooking and heating, while higher income groups use firewood for barbeque and heating using open fireplaces. However, it is worth pointing out that the high consumption of firewood does not necessarily translate into high commercial demand of firewood, particularly in the rural areas, as most households prefer collecting firewood for own use instead of purchasing it.

Wholesalers and small-scale retailers, shops, kiosks and open-air stalls

The marketers and suppliers of the main cooking and heating energy sources in Namibian market can be categorised as wholesalers or as small-scale businesses comprising retailers, kiosks and open-air stall sellers. According to the baseline survey, these two groups play a very critical role in the supply and distribution of cooking and heating energy sources particularly of firewood and charcoal.

Wholesalers

A total of 5 respondents from wholesalers participated in the project's baseline survey, where the majority of the participants were men (4 respondents). More than 60% of the respondents in the wholesaler group were less than 40 years old, were mostly male (80%), and located in peri-urban and rural areas. It can be assumed that this relatively young, active age group and gender dominates the wholesaling section of the cooking and heating energy sources, particularly of firewood and charcoal, due to the rigorous activities this section entails that includes travelling, loading and off-loading, distribution and so on.

The respondents from the wholesalers' survey cited **high demand, favourable supply price** and **good quality of products** as the main reasons for venturing into firewood and charcoal businesses respectively. Asked about the modes of payment they accepted, **60% and 40%** of the respondents from the wholesalers' survey stated that they **accept cash up front and bank transfers respectively**.

Despite the respondents from the wholesalers' survey indicating that they receive orders from their customers **via phone, most** of them stated that they **do not offer delivery services to their customers** indicating that most of the wholesale businesses still preferred purchases that are directly from their premises.

Asked about the **main factors that they thought influenced their customer's choice** of energy sources 40% of the respondents from the wholesaler survey stated **affordable price** and **accessibility** in terms of availability and access as the main factors. They also mentioned **good quality of product and convenience** as other factors that also influenced their customers' choice.

Regarding the **effects of COVID-19 pandemic** on their businesses, respondents from the wholesaler indicated that the pandemic had affected their businesses as it led to a **low demand** for their products.

Small-scale retailers, shops, kiosks and open-air stalls

The results of the baseline statistical survey indicated that most respondents in the **small-scale businesses** category fall under the age group (30-60 years) revealing

that this role has been taken up by both the young (<40 years) and the old (>50 years). Respondents of the survey are **mostly men**. The survey results further indicated that most of the small-scale businesses comprising retailers, kiosks and open-air stall sellers are located in **urban areas**. It could be assumed that this is as a result of a high demand for the cooking and heating energy sources in the urban areas compared to rural areas mainly because the urban dwellers are not able to collect the energy source by themselves for their own use. In addition, most of the respondents in the small-scale businesses group indicated that they were managers, meaning they did not own the business but had been employed to run the business on behalf of the owners.

The respondents from the small-scale business survey indicated that convenience or practical use, affordability in price, accessibility in terms of availability in markets and physical access, are the most relevant factors that their customers consider when deciding which energy source to buy. Moreover, 53% and **33%** of the respondents from small-scale businesses ranked **firewood and LPG gas** respectively as the first energy source option for their customers for heating and cooking whereas **33% and 40% ranked firewood and charcoal respectively as the second option**. Asked about their customers, 80% of the respondents in the small-scale business survey indicated **households** and 13% indicated **local businesses**. The baseline statistical survey revealed that **most of the customers** of the small-scale businesses bought the energy source directly from the shop and that 93% of the small-scale businesses **do not sell to international customers**. As was the case with wholesaler respondents this group also indicated that they neither offer delivery services suggesting that the practice is yet to pick up.

The majority of the small-scale businesses indicated that they prefer to sell firewood and charcoal because of the **favourable supply price, reliable supply, and high demand**. They further mentioned **convenience and practicality, affordability in price** and the **accessibility to the products** as the most relevant factors that their customers consider when choosing a specific energy source.

Regarding the **effects of COVID-19 pandemic** on their businesses, respondents from the group of small-scale retailers indicated that the pandemic had affected their businesses as it led to a **low demand** for their products.

Charcoal and/or firewood

According to the results of the baseline statistical survey **65% and 60% of the households** in Namibia indicated that they use **firewood and electricity** respectively for cooking and heating purposes. In addition, 20% and 10% of the

households further reported that they use LPG gas and charcoal respectively as their main energy source for cooking and heating, indicating that charcoal is not so popular as an energy source when compared to firewood.

The baseline statistical survey revealed that **firewood is mainly used for cooking** (approx. 57% of respondents), **barbecuing** (40% of respondents) and **water heating** (approx. 37%) depending on whether the household lives in a **rural or urban setting**. This is in line with a report by Frank and Nuulimba (2016) which indicated that rural households in Namibia predominantly use firewood for cooking (86%) and heating (75%), compared to about 20% of urban households who use firewood for cooking and heating. In contrast only about **4-8% of rural households claimed to use electricity compared to 75% of the urban households**. Moreover, according to the report, lower income groups mainly use firewood for cooking and heating while the higher income groups use it mainly for barbeque wood (the traditional braai fuel) or briquette and heating at open fireplaces (Helbig & Nuulimba, 2016). Regarding their usage of charcoal about 18% of the household **respondents mentioned braaiing/barbecuing** and while 10% mentioned ironing as the main uses.

Brands and labels

Most of the cooking and heating energy sources sold by Namibian wholesalers are **not branded**. In fact, **80% of the surveyed wholesalers** indicated that the fuel they sell has **no brand**. In contrast, **53% of the small-scale retailers, kiosks and open-air stall sellers** reported that they sell branded cooking and heating energy sources.

When asked about the **important characteristics** they would look for in any brand of cooking and heating energy sources, the small-scale business respondents indicated **fair price** and **the ease of accessing** the brand as the most important considerations. In addition, they also mentioned **reliability in the supply** of the brand as well as its **environmental friendliness**.

The results of the baseline survey are in line with previous reports on branding and packaging of Namibian cooking and heating energy sources particularly charcoal and firewood. For instance, a report by MITSMED (2016) indicated that Namibian barbecue charcoal enters the consumer market under more than **15 different brand** names, but that only a few of the brands were registered in Namibia (e.g., Jumbo, Etosha and Savannah). According to the report the Namibian trademarks were owned by the processors located close to the production areas, whereas the remaining brands entered the market through foreign brand names (MITSMED, 2016).

Supply chain

The respondents in the wholesalers' survey indicated that they had between **1-5 suppliers for both charcoal and firewood** of which on average one to two were charcoal suppliers and one was firewood supplier. Furthermore, they indicated that most of these suppliers were either located in the same town, within the country, or in the neighbouring country, and that they placed their orders to the suppliers either via **phone call, social media, or by visiting and ordering directly from the distribution centres**. Asked about the main reason why they chose a certain supplier, the wholesaler respondents cited **reliable supply**. Most of the respondents from the wholesaler group indicated that they experienced no problems in sourcing their products.

On their part, 40% of the respondents from the small-scale businesses indicated that they mostly had **one supplier and 1-3 suppliers of firewood and charcoal** respectively. Furthermore, **47%** of the respondents indicated that their suppliers were located within the **same country**, whereas **20%** indicated that their suppliers were located within the **same city** and that they mostly ordered their products **via phone**. Asked whether they experienced any problems in sourcing the product, **67% of the respondents** from the small-scale businesses indicated that they **did not have any problems** whereas **27%** indicated that they experienced **some problems especially during winter**.

Price and packaging

For the wholesale sector as well as the small-scale businesses in Namibia, in terms of pricing the baseline survey was only able to capture the minimum and maximum values of the quantity and cost instead of averages (means) since there was a lot of variation among the data values and most participants of the survey did not respond to the questions in the section. Thus, the baseline survey did not offer reliable results on the pricing of the different energy sources, nor did it offer reliable results on the demand and price fluctuation due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The information provided below regarding prices and packaging was obtained from other sources of data collection.

Firewood is sold in fuel stations, by sellers or in supermarkets in branches or in logs. According to the baseline survey, the wholesaler and small-scale business respondents indicated that they sell firewood and charcoal in **units of bundles and kilograms** respectively.

Helbig and Nuulimba (2016) indicated that, in most cases, branches are traded as 10-20 kg bundles. However, some supermarkets package and sell firewood in bags, a practice that is still not widespread (Helbig & Nuulimba, 2016). Firewood

prices in Namibia vary depending on the region and the setting i.e., whether urban, peri-urban or rural. Helbig and Nuulimba (2016) indicated that a bundle of wood containing six pieces of wood sold for an average of 10 N\$ (0,60 €). According to this study, the bundle was roughly enough fuel to cook a typical meal for about six

Wholesalers indicated that cooking and heating energy sources they sold were either too expensive, difficult to access or unsafe to handle or store

people. The DAS report (2020) estimated that the average firewood **prices per tonne range between 900 N\$ (54 €) and 1,400 N\$ (84 €)** (DAS, 2020).

In terms of packaging, firewood as well as charcoal are usually sold in a bundle or per kilo. Only very few Namibian producers are involved in retail packaging for the end consumers, despite the fact that this could help add value to the product (DECOSA, 2015). In 2016 Namibia had about **10 charcoal processors** (MITSMED, 2016). Some Namibian trading companies are involved in retail packaging for direct exports to overseas markets. The few larger charcoal processors involved in the packaging of charcoal particularly destined for export to overseas markets (MITSMED, 2016) have large-scale screens and bagging facilities that they use to pack the charcoal.

According to DECOSA (2015) and MITSMED (2016), 50% of the charcoal is exported in 50kg bags to South Africa. Europe is also a key importer of Namibian charcoal. The markets for barbeque charcoal (particularly in Europe) have been under-supplied for years and the gap between demand and supply keeps increasing. As a result of this increasing demand, the price of Namibian charcoal destined for the European market has continued to increase. In 2015 Namibian producers received 1,850 N\$ per tonne of charcoal (DECOSA, 2015).

Challenges with existing cooking and heating energy sources

Most of the wholesalers (60%) in the baseline survey indicated that they were **satisfied with the cooking and heating energy sources that they sold** with the majority indicating that they were satisfied with firewood (60%) followed by charcoal (40%). However, the wholesaler respondents who were unsatisfied indicated that the cooking and heating energy sources they sold were either **too expensive, difficult to access (far distance to supplier), or unsafe to handle or store** (they can easily result in fire accidents, pollution and breathing problems if not well handled or stored). This means that the wholesalers had problems with far-away suppliers as this resulted in them having to incur high transports costs in securing the product and unreliability of their suppliers.

Small-scale businesses comprising retailers, kiosks and open-air stall sellers indicated in the baseline survey reported that they were **either very satisfied** (40%) or **satisfied** (53%) with the cooking and heating energy sources they sold, showing a very high level of satisfaction. Questioned on their level of satisfaction with the different energy sources they sold, 40% and 53% of the respondents from small-scale businesses indicated that they were **very satisfied and satisfied** respectively with firewood as a product, meaning that for an overwhelming majority of them it was economically profitable to sell firewood and they were therefore content. Around 53% of respondents indicated that they were satisfied with charcoal as a product. Comparing the two energy sources, it can be assumed that the majority of the small-scale businesses were more content in selling firewood over charcoal. This could be because firewood has higher returns or profit margins, a reliable supply and a stable demand or simply because they found it easier to handle compared to charcoal.

Asked about the challenges that they faced in their business, the small-scale businesses cited competition from too many businesses, **brand dominion, theft of their product** (particularly wood), **insufficient stock** that easily runs out, and concerns about **deforestation** as main challenges.

On their part, the **households** in the baseline survey also mentioned some challenges they faced with the different cooking and heating energy sources that they use. About 17% of the respondents cited **long travel distances**, 15% indicated that it is **hard to find**, about 7% said it is **unhealthy**, 5% cited **inconsistency in its availability**, and finally 5% indicated that it is **expensive**.

Consumer preferences (households)

The sample size for the analysis of households in Namibia encompasses 60 respondents, of which around 62% were male and 38% female. About 57% of the respondents were between 20 and 50 years old, 55% were heads of their household, and 53% had secondary education. Most household respondents were located in urban (36.7%) and rural areas (33.3%) (Table 11).

Location	Residential area	Percentage
Urban	Windhoek	36.7
Peri-urban	Otjiwarongo	30.0
Rural	Ovitoto	33.3

Table 11 Household respondents by location (%)

Regarding the living conditions of the household respondents, about **97%** indicated that they owned their home, 53% have **pipled water**. Most of the respondents reported that they have both an electric **stove or electric hot plate (47%)** and **a fireplace outside (48%)**, indicating that they mostly used a mix of energy sources for cooking. The most dominant energy sources for cooking mentioned by the respondents are electricity (60%) and firewood (65%). Other energy sources are LPG (20%) and charcoal (10%).

For the households, general factors that influence decisions to choose energy sources are **efficiency of the product, price of the product, reliability in the supply of the product, and its suitability for all weather**. The other factors that were mentioned though to a lesser extent, included **convenient access to suppliers, safe to handle/store and environmentally friendly**.

The survey found, the most popular energy source used by the households is firewood followed closely by electricity. **Firewood** is used mostly for cooking, braaiing/barbecuing, water heating and for small home-based income generating activity/production as well as ironing and space heating. **Electricity** is used mostly for ironing, cooking, water heating, and for small home-based income generating activity/production and space heating (see Table 12).

Household activities	Most popular energy sources used
Cooking	Firewood and electricity
Space heating	Firewood and electricity
Water heating	Electricity and firewood
Barbecuing (Braaiing)	Firewood and charcoal

Table 12 Energy sources used for household activities

Purchasing was the **main method of securing the energy source** with 50% of the household respondents indicating that they **purchased the product** (see Figure 8).

Figure 8 Method of Obtaining / Accessing Energy Source

Most household respondents indicated that **good price, efficiency of the energy source** and **reliable supply** are the most important factors they considered when deciding on the energy sources, particularly firewood. This is in line with the findings in most established reports which indicate that **price** and **supply reliability** are the two major influencing factors. Other factors such as **environmental friendliness, safety in using, handling and storing** of the fuel as well as the **ease in transporting** the fuel were also mentioned by the respondents as factors that they considered, though to a lesser extent.

Out of the households that purchase their cooking and heating energy sources, about 40% of the respondents indicated that they purchase the energy sources mainly from **local kiosks or vendors**, while 18% indicated from **supermarkets**. Based on this, it can be assumed that particularly in **urban and peri-urban areas local kiosks and vendors provide a good opportunity** for the commercialisation of the solid biofuel.

In terms of transportation of the cooking and heating energy sources, parents were the main responsible persons for transporting energy sources from vendors, supermarkets, or shops.

About 52% of the respondents indicated that they were either “very satisfied” or “satisfied” with the energy source they were using, while about 32% “very dissatisfied” or “dissatisfied”. The main reasons cited for this dissatisfaction included “long distance travel” and “it’s hard to find”.

About 90% of the household respondents indicated that they had heard about solid biofuels, citing social group/cooperative, radio and social media as the channels through which they heard about it. In fact, 58% of respondents indicated that they were currently using biofuel or had used it before. Wood was the most common solid biofuel the respondents were using. About **92% of the respondents said they would consider testing a new type of biofuel** as part of the SteamBioAfrica project, with about 48% indicating that affordability (cost) would be the main motivation for switching to a new biomass fuel. Certainty in supply-availability, environmentally friendliness, and low residues and waste’s potential (ash) were also mentioned by the households as reasons that could motivate them to switch to new biomass fuel.

3.1.3 SOUTH AFRICA

Cooking and heating energy sources

According to results of the baseline survey, in the Republic of South Africa the use of energy sources for cooking and heating varies depending on the locations. In **urban** areas respondents indicated they use an energy mix, mainly composed by electricity, LPG. In **peri-urban** areas, 50% of the household respondents indicated they too use an energy mix, which usually consists of electricity, complemented either by firewood or gas. In **rural** areas, 53% of respondents reported to use an energy mix. The mix consisted mostly of electricity, and was complemented with firewood, and paraffin or LPG. Those, who did not have an energy mix, relied either purely on electricity, firewood or paraffin.

Commercialisation of charcoal and firewood

Firewood is a popular cooking and heating, particularly in rural areas, but the consumption of firewood is also relatively high in peri-urban areas. **Charcoal**, on the other hand, is mainly used by household consumers in urban areas (see Figure 9).

Figure 9 Charcoal and firewood usage by location (%)

Similar as in Botswana and Namibia charcoal is mostly used for leisure activities such as barbecues (braai'ing) and other social activities. It is worth highlighting that South Africa is an important importer of charcoal, particularly from Namibia. To a large extent imported Namibian charcoal is re-packaged and exported to international markets in Europe. Local production of charcoal is mostly controlled by community-based enterprises, which supply wholesalers and distribution centres to cover part of the local demand.

Wholesalers and small-scale retailers, shops, kiosks and open-air stalls

Wholesalers

The baseline statistical survey targeted wholesalers from sub-urban areas (Alberton, Boksburg, and Germiston), surrounding the city of Johannesburg. All the respondents in the wholesalers' survey reported that they sell energy sources for cooking and heating. They indicated that in terms of customer demand, **charcoal is the most important energy source**, followed by **firewood in second place**. The respondents further revealed that they resorted to selling the charcoal and firewood because of the **high demand** for both energy sources and that they preferred to sell charcoal because of its **good quality** and **environmentally friendliness**. Other factors that they considered important in choosing charcoal as a product included **convenient access to suppliers** and **low supply price**.

Good quality was also an important factor they considered when choosing to deal in firewood as a product. The wholesaler respondents mentioned that they sell charcoal in kilograms and firewood in bundles.

When asked about the most popular types of cooking and heating energy in the wholesaler's area, 60% of the respondents indicated that **charcoal** was by far **the most popular energy source**, followed by **LPG gas, paraffin/kerosene** and lastly by **firewood**. Moreover, the respondents from the wholesaler group indicated that they perceived **good quality (i.e., good burning and heating), longevity, common use and affordable price** as the most important factors their customers considered in choosing any particular energy source.

Almost all the wholesaler respondents indicated that their businesses were affected by the **COVID-19** pandemic, particularly due to supply chain shocks resulted in **unreliable supplies and increased prices**. They also cited low demand and closure of their stores due to lockdowns as some of the other challenges they had to grapple with during the pandemic.

The wholesalers stated that their customers mostly buy their products in their **shops** and from **street vendors**, and that they also received some orders via social media (Facebook, WhatsApp) or by phone though to a lesser extent.

About 60% of the wholesaler respondents indicated that they do **not offer a delivery service**, whereas the few that offer delivery services reported that they generally do not charge any extra fee for this service and that they usually deliver the product within the same day. When asked if the prices of cooking and heating energy sources had changed in the last year (due to the pandemic), 50% of the wholesaler respondents stated yes and the other half answered no.

The respondents from the wholesaler survey revealed that their main customers were local companies and, to a lesser extent, local resellers and retailers. Moreover, the respondents indicated that they do not supply or sell to international customers. Regarding the gender of their customers, the wholesaler respondents reported that their customers were from both genders. Finally, 100% of the respondents reported that their customers mostly **pay cash up front** for the product. Only one wholesaler reported to offer **payment by mobile phone**.

Small scale retailers, kiosks and open-air stalls

In the baseline survey in RSA, 70% of the respondents from small-scale businesses (including small scale retailers, kiosks, open air stalls) reported that they sold energy sources for cooking and heating. About 80% of the respondents from this

group of small-scale businesses indicated that their business is located in **peri-urban areas** of Katlehong and Tokoza around Johannesburg, the economic and financial centre of South Africa, while the remaining 20% were located in rural areas in King William's Town. About 30% each of the surveyed small-scale businesses indicated that they were **supermarkets and kiosks**, 20% were **petrol stations**, while 50% of the shops and stalls were located in **local markets**. Furthermore, 30% of respondents indicated that their shop was **located on the roadside** while 20% reported that their shop was **located in the owner's house**.

Asked to rank the **cooking and heating energy sources** they sold based on the customer demand, **firewood together with paraffin/kerosene** ranked **first, followed by charcoal and thereafter LPG gas**. The respondents from the small-scale businesses indicated that they preferred to deal in paraffin/kerosene mainly because of its reliable supply and favourable price. In addition, they also cited high demand, convenient access to suppliers and safe handling/storage as important factors that also influenced their choice of this product. Regarding firewood and charcoal, the respondents indicated that they preferred to sell these particularly because of their favourable supply prices. Moreover, the surveyed respondents indicated that reliable supply and environmental friendliness also influenced their choice of firewood, while convenient access to suppliers and safe handling/storage was a factor they considered in choosing charcoal.

When asked about the **most popular energy sources for cooking and heating** in the small-scale business areas, the respondents indicated LPG gas and paraffin/kerosene first, followed by charcoal as second most popular energy source, and finally firewood. The respondents further indicated that they perceived **affordable price and convenience/practicality** of use as the primary considerations by their customers in choosing the energy source and that to **a lesser extent good quality also plays a role**.

With regard to **COVID-19**, 50% of the respondents from the small-scale businesses survey indicated that it resulted in **price increases** while 40% reported that it **led to unreliable supply and low demand**, reflecting the same issues as mentioned by respondents from the wholesalers group. Surprisingly, 30% of the respondents from the small-scale businesses reported that their business was not affected at all by COVID-19.

Around 80% of respondents from small-scale businesses survey indicated that they sell their products in a shop/kiosk/stand while 20% reported to sell through street vendors. **None of them offer a delivery service** for their products.

80% of the respondents also reported that the prices of cooking and heating energy have changed in the last year (2021) but did not indicate which factors influenced the price changes. Regarding their main customers, **100% of the respondents** from the small-scale businesses indicated that their main customers were **private households**, **20% cited local businesses**, and **none reported having international customers**.

The results of the small-scale businesses survey in RSA revealed that 80% of the main contacts for the sale of cooking and heating energy are men and that 80% of the customers to the small-scale businesses were women. According to the respondents, predominantly more men are owners of a shop, stall or kiosk selling cooking and heating energy sources, which is in line with the **respondents themselves**, out of which 30% who reported being women also reported being employees, managers or partners, while 70% were men and at the same time owners.

Charcoal and/or firewood

Of the respondents from the **wholesalers' survey**, **60% reported that they sell charcoal, with all of them sourcing their charcoal locally from South Africa**. Although 60% of the respondents indicated that the **demand for charcoal** in their areas is **mostly constant**, the respondents who do not sell charcoal cited low demand for charcoal as the main reason for not selling charcoal.

When asked about the main challenges they faced in working with charcoal in their area, the respondents from the wholesalers' survey indicated that the physical component of charcoal seems to be a key feature for commercialisation. The respondents indicated **heavy carrying as the main barrier** and the **high costs associated with transportation**. All of the respondents from the wholesalers group indicated that they would be open to selling a different type of cooking and heating energy source.

In the small-scale businesses survey 50% of the respondents confirmed that they sell charcoal with all of them indicating that they source the charcoal locally from South Africa. The respondents who do not sell charcoal in this category cited perceived **low demand** and an **unreliable supply as the main reasons for not selling charcoal**. In line with the wholesalers, 50% of the respondents in the small-scale business survey stated that there is a **constant demand for charcoal** in their area, whereas 30% of the respondents also reported that it is **seasonal with clear high and low seasons**.

Asked to rank the main challenges with the use of charcoal in the area, the small-scale businesses reported that the main challenges were that it is **too costly** and **not healthy**. Finally, 70% of the respondents from the small-scale business survey indicated that they would be open to considering selling a different type of energy source.

Brands and labels

The results of the baseline statistical survey in RSA revealed that **branding** of cooking and heating energy sources **is not important for the wholesalers'** group with none of them indicating that the cooking and heating energy source they sold had a brand. When asked about the relevance of brands to their customers, 30% indicated that it was not important, while 70% indicated they did not know. Although no brand was specifically mentioned by the respondents, they listed **reliable supply, environmental friendliness, good quality and a fair price as key characteristics they would look for in a brand**.

As with wholesalers, the **small-scale businesses survey also revealed that none of the businesses sold branded cooking and heating energy sources**. Nevertheless, 50% of the respondents answered that a brand is relevant to them, while the other 50% reported it is not. When asked if brands are important to their customers, 50% answered yes, 30% answered no and the rest did not know. Again, while no brand was specifically mentioned, the respondents indicated that a **fair price** was the most **important characteristic in a brand**, followed by **reliable supply** and, to a lesser extent, ease of access, i.e., having the source readily available.

Supply chain

When wholesalers were asked how many suppliers they had in total, the information was relatively evenly distributed between **one and four**. For **charcoal and firewood**, however, the average number of **suppliers is specifically two**. Orders for products are primarily placed via phone calls and distribution centres, followed to a lesser extent by web-based approaches such as social media, an app or the website. Wholesalers' main suppliers are usually located in the next city. The main reasons for choosing their suppliers are **good prices**, followed by **reliable supply and good quality**. **None** of the wholesalers **reported having problems sourcing their products at any time of the year**.

The number of suppliers ranges from **one to three** for the different energy sources. Similar to wholesalers, ordering of products is mainly carried out through **telephone calls** and **distribution centres** with the fact that their main suppliers

are from the same area. When sourcing products, 40% of small-scale businesses reported having no seasonal difficulties, while some of them had challenges in **summer** and in winter.

Price and packaging

The baseline statistical survey showed that prior to the pandemic (2019), the cost to wholesalers of firewood ranged from ZAR 550 (33 €) to ZAR 875 (53 €) per tonne and that of charcoal ranged from ZAR 1050 (63 €) to ZAR 1500 (90 €) per tonne, whereas other energy sources would cost between ZAR 740 (44,62 €) and ZAR 750 (45,23 €) per tonne. During the pandemic (2020-2021), firewood

Wholesalers reported that they sold between 11 and 40 tonnes of charcoal per month before the pandemic and 12 to 50 tonnes during the pandemic

prices increased slightly but remained within the above figures, while charcoal prices increased substantially to between ZAR 1400 (84 €) and ZAR 2800 (169 €) per tonne. Prices for other energy sources remained unchanged. This suggests that **charcoal is relatively expensive compared to other energy sources.**

When asked at what price wholesalers sold their products to their customers before the pandemic, the average price for a kilogram of charcoal ranged from ZAR 3 (0,18 €) to ZAR 6.5 (0,39 €) and for a kilogram of alternative energy sources from ZAR 2.5 (0,15 €) to ZAR 2.8 (0,17 €). During the pandemic (2020-2021), the price of charcoal increased to sell for an average of ZAR 5 (0,30 €) to over ZAR 8 (0,48 €) for a kilogram.

On average, **wholesalers bought about 20 tonnes of firewood and 20 tonnes of charcoal per month** before the pandemic, although there was one wholesaler who also bought larger quantities (50 tonnes) per month. During the pandemic, this number did not change significantly, which means that wholesalers continued to buy their usual quantities.

On average, the respondents in the wholesaler's survey reported that they **sold between 11 and 40 tonnes of charcoal per month before the pandemic** and 12 to 50 tonnes during the pandemic, so there was even a slight increase in sales figures.

The small-scale business survey revealed that prior to the pandemic (2019), the **cost** to small businesses for firewood ranged from ZAR 900 (54 €) to ZAR 20000 (1206 €) per tonne and for charcoal from ZAR 8000 (482 €) to ZAR 28500 (1719 €) per tonne. During the pandemic (2020 - 2021), figures for firewood remained the

same, while charcoal prices ranged from ZAR 7000 (422 €) to ZAR 25700 (1550 €) per tonne due to minimal price changes. When asked at what **price small businesses sold** their products to their customers before the pandemic, the average price for a kilogram of firewood ranged from ZAR 2 (0,12 €) to ZAR 20 (1,21 €) and for charcoal from ZAR 7 (0,42 €) to ZAR 9 (0,54 €). Surprisingly, the selling price of firewood and charcoal did not change during the pandemic (2020-2021).

Before the pandemic, respondents from small-scale businesses **indicated that they purchased monthly quantities** of between 250 kg and two tonnes of firewood and between 50 and 200 kg of charcoal on average. These figures increased during the pandemic to between 250 kg and four tonnes of firewood and between 50 kg and 400 kg of charcoal. The respondents further indicated that before the pandemic, **the quantities they sold** averaged between 125 kg and 4 tonnes of firewood and 30 kg to 400 kg of charcoal per month and that during the pandemic, this changed to 80 kg to 125 kg of firewood and 30 kg to 100 kg of charcoal sold per month.

Challenges with existing cooking and heating energy sources

Around 90% of the respondents in the wholesalers' survey stated that they were very satisfied with the cooking and heating energy source they sold. Specific to the cooking and heating energy sources, 30% and 10% of the respondents indicated that they were very satisfied with charcoal and firewood respectively. The survey did not reveal deeper challenges with the commercialisation and marketing of cooking and energy sources. In any case, overall, 70% of the survey respondents indicated that they were open to offering a new type of cooking and heating energy source to be provided under this project.

When asked about how satisfied they were in general with the cooking and heating energy sources they sold, 70% of the small-scale businesses indicated that they were **very satisfied** while the remaining 30% reported that they were **satisfied**. Regarding the specific cooking and heating energy sources, the respondents from the small-scale business survey were particularly very satisfied with charcoal and paraffin/kerosene, followed by firewood and LPG gas with 30% each. When asked about the factors that made them dissatisfied with charcoal, the respondents cited too high prices, unreliable supply and too much competition. For firewood they mentioned low demand, and for LPG gas they stated too expensive, and finally for paraffin/kerosene they indicated being unsafe to handle/store. Also in this case, 70% of the respondents were willing to participate in a trial of selling a new type of energy source for cooking and heating.

Consumer preferences (households)

Due to problems in the data collection process, we suggest the following information regarding consumer preferences should be used with caution.

The sample size for the analysis of households in South Africa encompasses 39 respondents, of which 38.5% are male and 61.5% are female. The majority of the respondents (61.5%) reported having secondary school education. Around half of the respondents are over 40 years old and almost two thirds of the respondents (64%) are heads of their household. Most household respondents are located in rural (39%) and urban areas (36%) (see table 13).

Location	Residential area	Percentage
Urban	Katlehong	36
Peri-urban	Amalinda, Rondebult, Tokoza	25
Rural	Njakazi, Pirie Mission	39

Table 13 Geographical distribution of respondents (South Africa)

Regarding the respondents living conditions, 71% of the respondents indicated having their own house, 64% have **piped water**, and 49% of households have a **toilet flush system**. The most popular types of cooking facilities among respondents are **electric stoves or hot plates** (available in 64% of interviewed households), followed by gas stoves and to a lesser extent a **fireplace outside**. **Almost 80 %** of the surveyed **households** get their energy **in form of electricity**. Other popular energy sources are LPG gas (35.9%) and firewood (20.5%), while charcoal was mentioned to a lesser extent (5.1 %). Further energy sources not listed but mentioned by respondents included paraffin (18.0%).

However, many households use some form of energy mix. About 50% of the respondents in the **peri-urban** space used an energy mix, which usually consisted of electricity, either assisted by firewood or gas. The 50% respondents without an energy mix usually relied either purely on electricity or on “other”. 53% of respondents in the **rural space indicated that they used** an energy mix. It mostly consisted of electricity, with a mix of firewood, and paraffin or LPG. Those, who did not have an energy mix, relied either purely on electricity, firewood or paraffin. All respondents in the **urban area used** some sort of energy mix. It was also built around electricity, using mostly LPG or “other” as the second energy source.

Factors influencing decisions of households to choose **electricity** as a cooking and heating energy source are mainly its **efficiency** (capacity to cook food fast) (31% of respondents), followed by it being **suitable for all weathers** (13% of respondents) and its **price** (10% of respondents).

In terms of which energy sources are linked to which activities, results of the baseline survey indicate that **electricity** is on average the most used type of energy for a variety of activities with 69.2% respondents indicating that they use it for **cooking**, 56.4% for **space heating** and 69.2% for **water heating**, 53.9% for **small income-generating activities** in the household or 51.3% for **ironing**.

For **cooking**, 38.5% of respondents also reported that they use paraffin, 35.9% use LPG gas and 30.7% use firewood as preferred energy sources, but to a lesser extent. Regarding **barbecuing**, 25.6% of respondents use firewood as the preferred energy source, followed by 20.5% who use electricity and 15.4% who use charcoal.

Household activities	Most popular energy sources used
Cooking	Electricity, paraffin, LPG
Space heating	Electricity
Water heating	Electricity
Barbecuing (Braaiing)	Firewood, electricity and charcoal

Table 14 Energy sources used for household activities (South Africa)

Generally regarding the factors influencing the decisions of households on their selection of cooking and heating energy sources, 48.7% stated **price**, followed by 25.6% who indicated **convenience or practicality of using** a particular fuel. **Safety of use and handling** as well as **accessibility** of the fuel are considered less relevant, while environmental friendliness was not mentioned by any of the respondents as the most important factor in choosing a fuel.

In relation to energy consumption, buying patterns and habits, 59% of the household respondents reported **purchasing** their energy sources, while 33%, a smaller group reported to both **collect and purchase** the energy sources and only a minority of 7.7% reported to **exclusively collect** their energy sources.

When asked where they purchase their energy sources, one-third each of the respondents indicated that they buy it from supermarkets or market places, from local kiosks or vendors, or from other sources such as the internet.

Roughly speaking, the price per kg for charcoal is around ZAR 14.4 (0.87 €) and the price of firewood is approximately ZAR 14 (0.84 €). Around 59% of the interviewees are satisfied or very satisfied with the fuel they use. Respondents that are not satisfied with the energy sources they use indicate that reasons are the costly price of the energy sources and the **unsteady availability of the product**.

Surprisingly, **59% of the household respondents indicated they had not heard about solid biofuels before while** 41% reported they had heard of solid biofuels. 10.3% of those who had heard about solid biofuels heard about it through the community, 5.1 % each, heard about it on TV, social media and at work. Furthermore, 53.8 % of households' respondents indicated that they have never used solid biofuels before while only 18.0% indicated they were using solid biofuels at the time when the survey was being conducted. The households that had not used solid biofuels before and that did not use them reported various reasons for this, 35.9% indicated that they **use other energy sources** such as firewood or charcoal, 25.6% reported that they were **unaware** of biofuels and 12.8% stated that biofuels are **too costly**. Nearly 77% of the household respondents would be willing to try new types of biofuels as part of the project.

When asked what would motivate respondents to switch to a new biomass fuel, 61.5% indicated affordability, i.e., a **good price** ratio, as the most important factor, followed by 30.8% who cited ideological reasons such as the **environmental friendliness** of the product, i.e., providing significant climate, health and economic benefits. Finally, 94.8 % of the respondents indicated that they were willing to be contacted again to participate in trials of new consumer energy products and up to 25.6 % would be **willing to pay** to participate in the trial.

3.2 MAPPING EXISTING CHARCOAL VALUE CHAINS: BOTSWANA, NAMIBIA, SOUTH AFRICA

3.2.1 CONTRASTS AND SIMILARITIES

Botswana

Simplified value chain maps of firewood and charcoal are shown below. The mapping of the downstream part of biomass-based value chains, particularly charcoal and firewood, was undertaken to identify key actors that are active in the market. Charcoal and firewood value chains were selected for this analysis due to their similar characteristics to the solid biofuel produced by the SBA project, as compared to firewood or LPG. In particular, charcoal as a 'competing' product can offer its value chains to be used for the introduction of the new solid biofuel.

In Botswana, household consumers still use firewood for main sources of cooking and heating, particularly in rural areas, where the consumers' access to other types of energy sources tend to be limited. Firewood is the principal energy source used for cooking in 46% households in Botswana (Mphinyane et al., 2018). In rural areas, the number reaches up to 77%. It is estimated that Botswana produces 200 tonnes of firewood per annum.

In peri-urban and urban areas, household consumers generally have more access to electricity and LPG. This group of consumers use charcoal mainly for leisure activities such as barbecues and parties. Due to its relatively higher price compared to firewood, only this group of consumers can afford buying charcoal. However, many households in urban and peri-urban areas often use firewood when cooking traditional food. These consumers buy firewood from small retail shops, online shops and occasionally from gas stations where price tends to be slightly higher compared to small retail shops or online sellers.

In the charcoal value chain map, there are two other groups of consumers besides the peri-urban and urban households. Public institutions (schools, hospitals, prisons) and industrial users (iron melting) use coal and charcoal to generate energy. These two groups of buyers purchase charcoal directly from wholesalers in bulk, while households in urban and peri-urban areas purchase charcoal from supermarkets, online sellers and gas stations. Hence, targeting these consumers in the commercialisation of the solid biofuel will necessitate the SBA project to target wholesalers, supermarkets and small retail shops.

Figure 10 Value chain map of firewood in Botswana

Figure 11 Value chain map of charcoal in Botswana

Namibia

On the household level in Namibia, charcoal is generally used or consumed by household consumers living in urban and peri-urban areas. Charcoal is used for leisure activities such as barbecues and parties, and less as main energy sources at home. This is due to its price being relatively higher than firewood. However, many urban and peri-urban households still use firewood for cooking traditional food. In the value chain map (Figure 12), two main actors serving urban and peri-urban consumers with charcoal are identified, which are supermarkets, gas stations and minimarkets, which operate in the retailing stage of the value chains. According to Helbig & Nuulimba (2016), 600 small and medium-sized producers generate about 100,000 tonnes of charcoal per annum. Rural households, which tend to have lower income, use firewood mainly for cooking and heating (DECOSA, 2015; Helbig & Nuulimba, 2016). It is estimated that 550,000 tonnes of firewood are used in Namibian households per annum. Many households spend considerable amounts of money more for firewood than necessary because they purchase daily firewood amounts that tend to be more expensive (Helbig & Nuulimba, 2016).

Figure 12 Map of downstream part of charcoal value chain in Namibia

The majority of Namibia's charcoal is destined for export due to high international demand. The country has seen its charcoal exports grow steadily in recent years. In 2016, the export volume reached 160,000 tonnes, bringing Namibia into the top ten charcoal exporting countries in the world. The export volume continues to increase with more than 210,000 tonnes in 2019/20. Namibia's main markets include South Africa, United Kingdom, Germany, France and Greece (BCBU & N-BiG, 2021; DAS, 2018). This finding is reflected by the charcoal value chain map of South Africa where re-packaging and exporting of charcoal plays an important role.

In Namibia, charcoal is marketed as follows:

- Namibian or South African specialised trading companies buy the charcoal "ex- production" and transport it to their "factory" where it is graded before payment is made to the producer.
- Namibian trading companies re-pack the charcoal in 50kg bags for export, mainly to South Africa but also directly to overseas wholesalers.
- South African trading companies pack the Namibian charcoal in small bags (normally 4 or 5kg), as finally required by the end-consumers and sell them locally, but in most cases export them to overseas countries (DECOSA, 2015).

According to DECOSA (2015), only a few Namibian producers are involved in retail packaging for the end consumer. Some larger Namibian trading companies are involved in retail packaging for direct exports to overseas markets. However, 50% of the charcoal is exported in 50kg bags to South Africa.

South Africa

The firewood value chain in rural areas of South Africa looks rather similar to the value chain in rural areas of Botswana. However, urban and peri-urban areas of South Africa have substantially bigger markets for firewood. Firewood value chains tend to be more fragmented and have many routes to market (see Figure 8). Firewood comes in many forms (packaged and unpackaged). In general, rural, peri-urban and urban consumers in South Africa still use firewood for cooking and heating, though rural consumers tend to rely more on firewood than on any other types of energy source (electricity, LPG or charcoal).

Figure 13 Firewood value chain in South Africa

Similar to Botswana and Namibia, charcoal is mainly used by consumers in urban and peri-urban areas of South Africa for leisure activities such as barbecues (braai'ing) and parties. In these two areas, households have access to electricity and LPG and tend to use electricity and LPG as their main sources of energy for cooking and heating.

The charcoal is normally packaged and sold through retail channels such as small retail shops, supermarkets, and gas stations. Charcoal in South Africa is produced by community-based enterprises, which channel their locally produced charcoal to wholesalers and distribution centres. On the other hand, South Africa imports charcoal from Namibia, which partly are repackaged and then exported to international markets such as Europe.

Figure 14 Charcoal value chain in South Africa

DESIGNING A SUSTAINABLE VALUE CHAIN FOR THE NEW SOLID BIOFUEL NAMIBIA, BOTSWANA AND SOUTH AFRICA

4

For household consumers in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa, the existing cooking and heating energy sources are quite costly. The price of and stable access to energy sources are key problems identified during the baseline survey.

4.1 IDENTIFICATION AND ANALYSIS OF HOT SPOTS AND IMPACT GROUP PROFILING

4.1.1 HOTSPOT ANALYSIS OF HOUSEHOLD ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Hotspots affecting household consumers when buying energy sources for cooking and heating were analysed to gain understanding on key factors that influence consumer’s decision. Oertzen (2015) reported household consumption levels of wood/wood products and electricity in rural and urban areas of Namibia for cooking and space heating, as a case in point (see Figure 15). The size of bubbles represents the levels of household consumption of wood/wood products and electricity.

Figure 15 Comparison of household consumption of wood/wood products and electricity for space heating and cooking

Results of the baseline survey that show aggregated data of Botswana, Namibia and South Africa about the most common energy sources used for cooking and heating in households in urban, peri-urban and rural settings. Results (see Figure 16) indicate that households in urban, peri-urban and rural areas mostly use electricity for heating and cooking. In addition, peri-urban and rural households rely, to a significant extent, on firewood and LPG. Even though the overall use of charcoal in the three areas is generally low, it is the highest in urban areas. This confirms that charcoal is not used in everyday life, but rather used for leisure activities.

Use of energy source in % of respondents

Figure 16 Use of energy source in % of respondents

Based on the analysis of the downstream value chain of cooking and heating energy sources, the energy usage trends in urban, peri-urban and rural areas can represent important challenges (hotspots) in the value chain development of solid biofuel. These potential challenges can affect the commercialisation of the SBA project proposed solid biofuel. On one side, households in rural areas largely depend on wood/wood products for cooking and space heating. However, in many cases these households can harvest firewood themselves as they need it. Hence, replacing firewood with solid biofuel “at cost” may require extra effort (e.g., incentives, enabling policy). On the other side, urban households, generally have higher disposable income, thus can afford using electricity for cooking and heating, may not see the benefits of using or switching solid biofuel. In addition, urban households may not have the cooking and heating facilities to use the solid biofuel. Most household respondents (more than 50%) indicated that they have never used solid biofuels before. Thus, households will not only have to be convinced to try a new energy source, but they may also need to make an investment to be able to use the new biofuel. This means that the pricing strategy of the solid biofuel is key.

Figure 17 shows results of the aggregated data of Botswana, Namibia and South Africa, in relation to customers' (households) perception of the problems of the cooking and heating energy sources they currently use. Most respondents identified the energy sources being costly as the main problem. Particularly in urban and peri-urban areas pricing plays a big role. In rural areas, respondents identified on top of the price, the distance to suppliers and the difficulties to find the product (unreliable supply) to be key problems related to the energy sources they use.

Supply chain problems from consumer side

Figure 17 Supply chain problems from consumer side in % - overall

To develop a value chain for the long-term commercialisation of the solid biofuel, it is important to take the hot spot analysis of households into consideration. This implies, on one side, developing a strategy that contemplates the urban and rural households' energy usage patterns, particularly the extensive reliance on electricity and LPG, the usage of charcoal limited to mostly leisure activities, and the market competition that firewood and charcoal would represent. In addition, it is key to tackle current challenges within the supply chain of cooking and heating energy sources. Concretely, this implies developing a pricing strategy, that allows capturing a part of the market share and allows competing with similar cooking and heating energy sources, such as charcoal and firewood, but also offering a stable and reliable supply and reducing the distances to access the product.

Hotspot analysis of wholesalers and retailers

In the wholesaling and retailing stages of the biomass-based value chains, many different actors have been identified. The hotspot analysis of wholesalers and retailers was undertaken based on the insights gathered in the baseline survey and observations of SBA project partners (BITRI, N-Big and Ekasi that represent Botswana, Namibia and South Africa respectively), which include factors such as the widely used (“popular”) energy sources, supply chains, pricing, packaging, labels and branding, consumer preferences, vendor characteristics, among others (for more information see Appendix 1).

The value chain analysis has shed light into hot spots regarding the downstream commercialisation of cooking and heating energy sources in regard to wholesalers and small-scale retailers. Tackling these hotspots will be key to develop a long-term commercialisation of the solid biofuel.

- Actors of the value chain tend to be mostly men, particularly managers of the wholesalers group. For small-scale retailers, the gender distribution was slightly more balanced, however, the majority were still men. A long-term commercialisation of the solid biofuel should promote gender inclusion and deliberately target the leadership and participation of women throughout the value chain.
- Most of the wholesalers and small-scale retailers do not offer delivery services. However, customers (households), particularly in rural areas, have identified the physical distance to the shops where they can access the cooking and heating energy sources they use as one of the main problems. This provides an opportunity to gain competitive advantage by offering scheduled delivery services or creating new formats like moving shops.
- A recurrent topic amongst households but also wholesalers and small-scale retailers is the unreliable supply and difficulties to access the energy sources, particularly in winter. The unreliability of the supply is an important challenge of existing value chains, addressing it offers a great opportunity for the long-term commercialisation of the solid biofuel. Thus, to position the solid biofuel it is key to offer a consistent and reliable supply of the product not only in urban areas, but especially in peri-urban and rural areas.

The downstream commercialisation of popular cooking and heating energy sources is controlled by a set of different actors. Figure 18 represents these actors in bubbles. The size of bubbles indicates the levels of power and interest of wholesalers and retailers (big and small) in influencing the consumption of cooking and heating energy sources by household consumers.

Market influence of wholesalers / retailers

Figure 18 Market influence of wholesalers / retailers

The Figure 18 (above) reveals potential challenges in the commercialisation and value chain development of solid biofuel:

- Wholesalers and big retailers (supermarkets) have substantially bigger influence in the biomass-based market. This group of value chain actors has the power (in terms of financial capacity and physical presence) to buy in bulk from producers and sell to consumers, as well as the interest to maintain their position in the market (market shares, brand reputation). Introducing a totally new product, i.e., solid biofuel, may not appeal to this group of value chain actors since there is not yet any demand for the solid biofuel. This poses risks for wholesalers and retailers alike.

- On the other hand, small sellers such as kiosks and open-air sellers tend to have low interest and power to influence the market. This group of value chain actors has limited market share and physical presence to be able to influence consumers. These value chain actors tend to only serve household consumers.
- Small online sellers seem to have more power (a wide digital outreach), especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, when household consumers prefer the convenience of online transactions. Similarly, they may have limited interest in trying out the new solid biofuel. Since online sellers often do not have physical shops, it can be challenging to reach out to them for placing the new solid biofuel on their online shops.
- Placing and marketing of the new solid biofuel at gas stations tends to be less challenging since gas stations sell many different types of fuels (firewood, charcoal, gasoline). However, since this type of retailer only relies on consumers coming to the stations, they have relatively low power in influencing consumers to try out new products, i.e., solid biofuel.

Based on the above, big retailers (supermarkets), wholesalers and exporter/importers can help create initial demand for the biofuel to support the replication of the SHS technology in the three target countries (see Figure 14 on Solid biofuel commercialisation strategies).

4.1.2 COMMERCIALISATION AND VALUE CHAIN DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES

Insights generated by the hotspot analysis provide a basis for the impact group profiling (see 2.2.3) which, in turn, can help the project develop strategies to address household consumers as well as wholesalers and retailers in the commercialisation efforts of the solid biofuel. The strategies will be adapted to what the SBA project seeks to achieve. In the SteamBioAfrica project, the objective is a wide-scale commercialisation of the solid biofuel. Since this commercialisation within the framework of the 3-year project can only be achieved if “strong” buyers or consumers are involved, this may necessitate the project to target industrial users as well as urban and peri-urban consumers. Their buying capacity may create a market demand that corresponds to the biofuel supply. Once the SHS technology has been replicated across the three target countries, the solid biofuel would become more available in the market which will tend to drive the price down. When this happens, the solid biofuel will become more accessible to consumers with low buying capacity such as people living in villages. Hence, there is a need to develop short, medium and long-term strategies for the commercialisation (Figure 19).

Solid biofuel commercialisation strategies

Figure 19 Solid biofuel commercialisation short, medium and long-term strategies

4.1.3 IMPACT GROUP PROFILING

Based on insights gathered from the hotspot analysis and baseline survey, it is possible to generate profiles of stakeholder groups that can help create impacts that the project seeks to achieve. Based on buying capacity and access to energy sources (Babalola & Opii, 2012), four impact groups can be identified (Figure 20). The first impact group with high buying capacity and high access to energy consists of industrial users such as iron melting (in Botswana), brewery, dairy and cement companies (in Namibia). The Ohorongu cement company in Namibia is reportedly running a programme to use woodchips as alternative fuel for the kiln. The cement plant has been equipped to replace up to 80% of coal, the original energy source of the kiln (DEG, 2015). The second impact group generally includes households in urban areas with high income and more access (Wiedinmyer et al., 2017; Nyembe, 2011) to any kinds of energy sources such as electricity, liquid petroleum gas (LPG), charcoal and firewood. The third impact group includes

households living in peri-urban areas, though this has to be treated with care since high-income households are also present in peri-urban areas such as in Gaborone, Botswana. The fourth impact group includes households living in villages or rural areas. These households tend to have limited access to energy sources due to their distance to towns and cities, coupled with low levels of income (Wiedinmyer et al., 2017; Nyembe, 2011). In the three countries it can be observed that people living in rural areas tend to heavily rely on firewood for cooking and heating.

For the purpose of wide-scale commercialisation efforts within the 3-year duration of SBA project, it may be concluded that urban and peri-urban consumers as well as industrial users are the most impactful groups (as represented by the size of bubbles in the figure below) in establishing value chains. This is due to their capacity to create market demand for the solid biofuel which, in turn, will sustain the upscaling or replication of the SHS technology. Once the technology is widely used, the solid biofuel will be more accessible also to other groups of consumers, i.e. rural communities.

Factors influencing household / end consumers

Figure 20 Factors influencing household/end consumers

Note: The size of bubbles does not indicate levels of access to energy or buying capacity. Instead, the location of bubbles in the chart indicates it.

The existing value chains of charcoal and firewood in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa present key challenges but also opportunities for the wide-scale commercialisation of the clean-burning solid biofuel.

— This value chain mapping and analysis has been undertaken with the objective of promoting and facilitating the commercialisation of the new solid biofuel which the SBA project seeks to introduce into the biomass-based markets in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa. The findings provide some initial insights into the existing biomass-based energy markets. Due to limitations related to the project's resource and timeframe, further research and studies into the biomass value chains will be needed to confirm these initial findings (that serve the SBA project's objectives)

It is important to consider that households should not be targeted as main consumers of the new biofuel and that they might need incentives to change to a different energy source.

and to further develop strategies for sustainable and long-term adoption and commercialisation of the new solid biofuel in the three countries. For now, it is possible to conclude that the existing value chains of charcoal and firewood in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa present important challenges but also opportunities for the commercialisation of the new solid biofuel.

In a general sense, findings of the analysis indicate that rural households commonly use firewood as one of the main sources of energy for heating and cooking. However, the commercial demand does not necessarily reflect the high usage of firewood in rural areas because many rural consumers collect firewood themselves. Urban and peri-urban households use electricity and/or LPG as their main source of energy for heating and cooking. In relation to firewood, charcoal is a costly cooking and heating energy source. Urban and peri-urban households commonly use charcoal only for leisure activities (barbecue, parties).

More specifically, urban and peri-urban population in **Botswana** relies highly on electricity and LPG for cooking and heating, and tend to only use charcoal for barbecuing. In rural areas, however, charcoal is rarely used since it is comparatively more expensive than firewood, which in many cases is collected by households themselves. Thus, to develop strategies for the commercialisation of the new solid biofuel in Botswana it is important to consider that households should not be targeted as **main** consumers of the new biofuel and that they might need incentives to change to a different energy source. To build up value chains for the long-term commercialization of the new solid biofuel, industrial users should be considered as the main consumer target group.

Namibia, is an important producer and exporter of charcoal. Charcoal is widely used by household consumers (by all levels of income) living in urban and peri-urban areas for leisure activities such as barbecues (braaiing). Charcoal is also

used by low-income households for cooking in pots and making traditional food. Nonetheless, the majority of Namibia's charcoal is destined for export due to high international demand. In relation to charcoal, firewood is a costly energy source. Despite it being highly popular in rural areas, the commercial demand for firewood is low because most households collect firewood themselves instead of buying it. Thus, the commercialisation of the new solid biofuel in Namibia will have to compete with the well-established charcoal industry and offer comparatively fairer prices than those of firewood. However, Namibia would also have great potential to use its existing charcoal export markets to export the new solid biofuel. This may allow open breaches for the large-scale commercialisation of the new solid biofuel and may even allow entering rural areas along the border in South Africa, where small-scale importers operate.

In **South Africa**, households in urban and rural areas use electricity and LPG as their main sources of energy for cooking and heating. Similar to Botswana and Namibia, charcoal is mainly used by consumers in urban (and to a lesser degree in peri-urban areas) for leisure activities such as barbecues (braai'ing). In addition, South Africa is a charcoal producer, importer and exporter country. Charcoal in South Africa is produced by community-based enterprises, which offer their product to wholesalers and distribution centres. The imported charcoal comes mainly from Namibia. It is partly repackaged and then exported to international markets, particularly in Europe. In 2019, the United Kingdom and the Netherlands were the two biggest importers of South African charcoal (World Bank, 2019). For a long-term commercialisation of the new solid biofuel, it is important to consider that households rely heavily on electricity and gas for cooking and heating, changing to a different energy source will require incentives. These incentives can be integrated in the retail and distribution sector for example by offering delivery services or alternative payment methods.

Namibia and South Africa are global exporters of charcoal, however, the domestic markets of charcoal in the two countries have not yet played a key role. Charcoal is mostly exported due to high demand in the international markets. Botswana, on the other hand, still imports most of its charcoal from Namibia and South Africa. Only recently some emerging community-based organisations (CBOs) started producing charcoal in Botswana. With the introduction and scaling up of the SHS technology and its new solid biofuel, Botswana, Namibia and South Africa can diversify and enhance the contribution of renewable energy in their energy mix.

Despite the many challenges, it is also possible to identify opportunities in existing value chains of cooking and heating energy sources, for the commercialisation of the new solid biofuel. It might be possible to use existing value chains of charcoal

(and to some extent of firewood) and improve identified 'hot spots' by offering an efficient, clean and affordable energy source alternative. For this, it is important to increase the attractiveness of the product by, for example, offering free delivery services, online selling systems, diverse payment options (cash, 'pay later' options, phone payments) and offer a reliable supply of the product, particularly in rural areas. Moreover, it is key to offer fair and competitive prices, especially in rural areas, where potential customers can use firewood, they collect themselves for free.

Attempts to complement or replace the consumption of firewood by rural households or the consumption of electricity and LPG by urban and peri-urban households will require careful marketing strategies. However, moving towards clean and renewable energy is key. The use of clean-burning solid biofuel will contribute to reducing CO² emission generated by the annual consumption of 100,000 tonnes of charcoal and 550,000 tonnes of firewood in Namibia alone. Not less important, replacing firewood and charcoal with the clean-burning solid biofuel will bring health benefits to households, particularly in rural areas.

Information gathered in this report reveals important patterns in the biomass value chains of the three countries, which can be further studied to support the development of sustainable biomass value chains that connect Botswana, Namibia and South Africa. Using this information, the project implementer will identify potential new business models as part of the commercialisation strategy that will support the scaling-up or replication of the SHS technology in Southern Africa. Particular attention will be given to micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) operating in the downstream part of biomass value chains, including MSMEs led by women and youth.

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Baseline survey questionnaires for (a) Wholesalers; (b) Small-scale retailers, kiosks and open-air stalls; (c) Households

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